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**PRACTICES AND PERCEPTIONS OF ENGLISH LANGUAGE TEACHERS ON
THE USE OF MULTIMEDIA MATERIALS FOR A COMMUNICATION COURSE IN
HIGHER EDUCATION**

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29 January 2023

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Acceptance Page

This paper prepared by **PAULA NADREA F. MORALES** with the title: “**PRACTICES AND PERCEPTIONS OF ENGLISH LANGUAGE TEACHERS ON THE USE OF MULTIMEDIA MATERIALS FOR A COMMUNICATION COURSE IN HIGHER EDUCATION**” is hereby accepted by the Faculty of Education, U.P. Open University, in partial fulfillment of the requirements for the Master of Arts in Language and Literacy Education.

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Biographical Sketch

Paula Nadrea F. Morales was born on May 27, 1988 in Paranaque, Metro Manila. Her family moved to Leyte in 1990, where she earned her education. She received her elementary education from Bagumbayan Elementary School and completed her secondary education from Hilongos National Vocational School. She earned her Bachelor of Arts in Communication Arts from the University of the Philippines in the Visayas Tacloban College (UPVTC). In pursuit for higher learning and excellence, she entered the graduate college of the University of the Philippines Open University to pursue a degree in Master of Arts in Language and Literacy Education, while teaching at the College of Arts and Sciences of the Visayas State University. She received a one-year thesis grant from the Commission on Higher Education under the K-12 Transition Program Scholarship. She is currently a member of Philippine Association of Language Teaching, Inc. (PALT) and Linguistic Society of the Philippines (LSP).

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-Paula Nadrea F. Morales

Dedication

This piece of work is heartily dedicated to God Almighty.

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ABSTRACT

There is a growing need to understand the practices and perceptions on the use of multimedia materials in higher education language classrooms, especially considering the pedagogical adjustments needed to address the changing needs of 21st century learners and to deal with disruptions such as the COVID-19 pandemic. As a potential contribution to addressing this need, this study focused on looking into the experiences and perspectives of language teachers tasked to teach a core course in Communication in selected state universities in the Philippines. Through hermeneutical phenomenology, the study examined the practices of using multimedia materials to deliver lessons in Purposive Communication. Data revealed that all teacher participants still predominantly use teacher-centered strategies, specifically lectures, although multimedia resources and interactive activities were incorporated. Most of the multimedia used by the teacher participants are standalone types and specifically fall under narrative media, the kind that supports learning through acquisition. Moreover, the TPACK and RAT frameworks were adopted to examine how multimedia are integrated. While findings from the data suggest an interest in using various multimedia, there were noted challenges to integrating such materials seamlessly. The most common challenge reflected troubleshooting problems, specifically navigating equipment and devices. The typical approach adopted to deal with the challenges in multimedia use was to consider their previous experiences and to rely on assistance from others. Based on these findings, policy recommendations and a training program on multimedia use for language teachers were suggested.

Keywords: Multimedia Materials, 21st century learners, Purposive Communication

Chapter I

Introduction

This chapter presents the background of the study and further elaborates the research gap observed. It tackles the need to explore the practices and perceptions of English language teachers on the use of multimedia materials in teaching a communication course. This presents the research questions and the research objectives of the study. It also discusses the significance of the study and its scope and limitations.

Background of the Study

Technology, as an active catalyst of change in today's globalized societies, generates impacts on different sectors, especially on education (Allen, 2019; Wardynski, 2020). Researchers claim that through the use of technology in the classroom, enhanced learning processes and outcomes are often acquired (Du Plessis & Webb, 2012; Eady & Lockyer, 2013; Georgiana & Olson, 2008; Purcell et al., 2013; Rana, 2013; Williamson & Payton, 2009). Consequently, technology provides an avenue for learners to acquire skills essential in the 21st century, which according to Stauffer (2020) include communication skills, information literacy, media literacy, and technological skills. This advancement in educational tools in the classroom plays a pivotal role in order for learners to acquire the necessary 21st century skills to cope with the growing demands of the contemporary world (Eaton, 2010).

The education sector of the Philippines, like any other country in the world, is in a dire compulsion to integrate technology into the curriculum to produce graduates who are equipped with 21st century skills (Gomez, 2001). Based on the curriculum

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revisions, nationwide policies (CMO no. 46-2012 and CMO no. 55-2016) were released to ensure that the quality of education being catered to in higher education would prepare every learner to face the competitive 21st century society.

To attain a quality curriculum and holistically develop the learners, the Commission on Higher Education (CHED) somewhat recently amended the General Education (GE) curriculum. The Commission on Higher Education implemented Memorandum Order no. 20 series of 2013 with the subject, “General Education Curriculum, Holistic Understandings, Intellectual and Civic Competencies”. This change in the GE curriculum was driven by the urgency to address and align the needs of 21st century learners to the necessities of today’s global market. The objectives set for this new curriculum require technology to be integrated with teaching the new GE courses to attain the Commission's goal.

One of the remarkable changes in the new GE curriculum is the smaller number of units offered. Most of the courses offered from the old curriculum were downgraded to senior high school; thus, the previously 64 units of GE courses have now become only 32 units. Since the commission intended not to offer repetitive courses from the senior high school, there is only one GE course offered for language and communication under this new curriculum, which is titled Purposive Communication (CMO 59-1996 in CMO 20-2013). Purposive Communication targets to develop the students’ communicative competence and enhance their cultural and intercultural awareness through multimodal tasks that provide them with opportunities to communicate effectively and appropriately to a multicultural audience in a local or global context. The knowledge, skills, and insights that students gain from this course may be used in their other academic endeavors, their chosen disciplines, and their

future careers as they compose and produce relevant oral, written, audio-visual and/or web-based output for various purposes” (CMO No. 20-2013).

As the course highlights the aim to develop the learners holistically, especially their communicative competence and multicultural awareness, teachers must expose learners to various resources like multimedia materials. According to some studies (Dubois & Vial, 2000; Gilakjani, 2012; Mayer & Moreno, 2003; Morrison et al., 2003; Sankey, 2006;), multimedia materials project diverse, authentic cultures and provide ample opportunities to enhance learners' communicative competence. In addition, multimedia materials can also aid in designing and providing interesting, engaging, and contemporary materials that would address the objectives of Purposive Communication. (Berk, 2009; Cuaresma, 2008; Erizar et al., 2018; Jacobson & Archodidou, 2000; Mayer, 2010; Olmeda, 2003; Paivio, 1990; Spiro & Jehng, 1990; Tan & Leong, 2003; ZHANG, 2016).

Thus, teachers of Purposive Communication must know about multimedia materials (e.g., precise multimedia material to be used for a specific topic, accurate timing in using multimedia materials in a lesson, and the likes), aside from their understanding and mastery of the content of the course in order to possibly deliver the lessons well. Nevertheless, the use of multimedia materials in language teaching has been growing globally (Bansagi & Rodgers, 2018; Blevins, 2018; Shoufan, 2019; Zhang, 2012); however, local studies remain relatively few. One study found is that of Fajardo (2014), investigating the actual use of multimedia materials to develop language skills in the Philippine context.

Although a more recent study from Eustaquio and Tandoc (2020) evaluated the readiness of college teachers to teach Purposive Communication and not specifically

delve deeper into the use of multimedia materials in teaching the course, it presented existing issues and concerns on instructional materials and technological tools experienced by the respondents in teaching Purposive Communication. In the study, authenticity, and applicability of instructional materials in relation to the use of technological tools and internet connectivity were cited as issues that concern the college teachers (Eustaquio & Tandoc, 2020). These claims were also experienced by other faculty who teach language courses using technology, as shown in research studies across the globe (Castillo, 2017; Cleaver, 2014; Johnson et al., 2016; Pazilah et al., 2019; Rahman, 2015; Sicilia, 2005; Tang, 2011; Toprakci, 2006; Yunus et al., 2009).

Considering the potential conflict between the need to use multimedia materials in teaching Purposive Communication and some challenges experienced by language teachers in integrating these technological tools, it is relevant to consider the perceptions and practices of English language teachers on the use of multimedia materials. Aside from the fact that there are fewer studies (Eustaquio & Tandoc, 2020; Fajardo, 2014; Gorra & Bhati, 2016; Tomaro & Mutiarin, 2018) conducted in the Philippine context regarding this field, it is also timely to explore this topic because the implementation of the GE curriculum in Philippine Higher Education remains in its early stages. At the same time, it would be relevant to delve into this topic in relation to the lessons learned from the COVID-19 pandemic where the use of information and communication technologies (ICTs), including multimedia materials, have increased. In addition, the current scenario of most education institutions in the Philippines where a form of blended teaching and learning or at least technology-enhanced teaching

calls for using multimedia resources, tools, and apps much more frequently and meaningfully.

Statement of the Problem

In particular, the GE core course, Purposive Communication, requires language teachers to employ multimedia materials in delivering the lessons since these materials would help meet the course and lesson objectives (CMO 20-2013; Fajardo, 2014; Tomaro & Mutiarin, 2018). However, language teachers experienced challenges like inadequate training, support, and access constraints (Johnson et al., 2016; Rahman, 2015) that either limit or hinder them from utilizing multimedia materials in the language classroom. So, digging deeper into the perceptions of language teachers on the use of multimedia materials in the language classroom and their actual practices are therefore appropriate and pertinent; in order to grasp a better understanding of the different factors (based on their perceptions and practices) which possibly hinder the teachers to utilize multimedia materials in their language classes effectively and to aid in properly addressing those impediments.

Research Questions

Inasmuch as there are issues observed in the utilization of multimedia materials in the language classroom, this study tried to answer the following research questions:

1. What strategies are used by selected language teachers in teaching Purposive Communication?
2. How do the teachers use or integrate multimedia materials in teaching Purposive Communication?
3. How do the teachers address the challenges they face in integrating multimedia materials in teaching Purposive Communication?

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Research Objectives

With the given research questions, this study aimed to achieve the following research objectives:

1. Describe the teaching strategies utilized by the language teachers in teaching Purposive Communication and categorize the type of strategy frequently used;
2. Classify the multimedia materials used by the language teachers in teaching Purposive Communication and provide the integration model employed by the language teachers; and
3. Discuss the challenges encountered by language teachers in integrating multimedia materials and identify the approaches employed by the language teachers to address the challenges faced.

Significance of the Study

This study explored teachers' perceptions and practices on multimedia materials integration in the language classroom, which were essential since the success of lessons in today's classroom relies on the teachers' knowledge of technology, pedagogy, and content and how these elements were incorporated.

This study had no direct impact on the teacher participants in terms of learning new methods and approaches in teaching; however, it opened an opportunity for introspection with their views and capabilities in using multimedia materials as tools in language teaching. The teacher participants were able to assess how they made use of technological tools like multimedia materials as well, which is significant in determining the success of language teaching with technology, as they were the ones who facilitated the incorporation of multimedia in their classes.

As this study focused on the perceptions and practices of teachers regarding the use of technology (multimedia) in Purposive Communication, which is an innovative course under the new GE curriculum in higher education, the curriculum and materials developers could utilize the findings of the study to review further and enhance the objectives, strategies, and materials imposed and suggested for this course.

Moreover, the growing literature on the quest of how technology, specifically the use of multimedia materials, can enhance language pedagogy by taking into account the perceptions of college English teachers and their actual practices in the classroom was enriched. Since the study delved into the views and knowledge of English teachers, a more vivid picture of the actual technology-language integration practices in the classroom was provided. A deeper understanding of how to effectively incorporate technology, pedagogy, and content based on the perceptions and practices of English teachers on multimedia materials integration was attained through this study.

With the current shift in the mode of teaching and learning brought about by the pandemic, this study could aid in reviewing the practices in the integration of technology in face-to-face classes, which can be used as a springboard for developing a policy for teachers' development.

Scope and Delimitations of the Study

This study focused on the practices and perceptions of college English teachers on using multimedia materials in language teaching. It delved into the practices and views of English teachers on multimedia only as a technological tool integrated into language teaching. The researcher based the answers to the research questions after

analyzing participants' responses to the survey questions, interviews, and class observation. So, any intervention and getting students' perspectives on the topic were not part of the concern of the study. All the participants were college English teachers from three state universities in Eastern Visayas.

The multimedia materials that were considered as part of the study included movies, music videos, video talks from lecture series or conferences, television shows or advertisements; multimedia presentations like PowerPoint presentations, digital flipcharts, and Interactive WhiteBoard; websites such as educational links or webpages, e-magazines, and e-newspapers; computer programs like mobile or computer games and software; and internet platforms, which include emails and blogs/vlogs, (Grzeszczyk, 2016).

Chapter II

Review of Related Literature and Conceptual Framework

This chapter provides an overview of Purposive Communication as a new GE course, along with the studies on the critical aspects of language teaching, which include: Instructional materials, teaching strategies, and assessment methods. This chapter also explores studies on technology integration models, which aid in evaluating the integration process of multimedia materials in the language classroom. This chapter also covers research on the effectiveness of technology integration in the language classroom, specifically multimedia materials. The chapter also deals with research studies on the perceptions and practices of teachers in integrating multimedia materials in the classroom. The challenges encountered in using technology (like multimedia materials) in the language classroom and the solutions used by the teachers to address these hindrances are also tackled. A few research instruments used in previous studies are also lightly discussed in this chapter to help guide the design of the instruments for this study. Lastly, the chapter describes the conceptual framework used as a blueprint of the study and presents the operational definition of terms.

Purposive Communication as a Relatively New GE course

Due to the significant shift in the undercurrents of basic education in the Philippines, there were amendments to the various curricula in higher education. Specifically, the shift required careful review of the GE curriculum to avoid repetition of courses that have been designed to be part of the senior high school curriculum (CMO 59-1996 CMO 20-2013). This shift also resulted in fewer units of GE courses

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offered in higher education. Aside from requiring amendments in the number of GE courses, the memo explicitly directed that all GE courses, including the language course, can be taught in English or Filipino. However, all state universities and colleges, including private higher educational institutions, were given the freedom to select the medium of instruction (CMO 20-2013).

Under the revised GE curriculum, only Purposive Communication (or Malayuning Komunikasyon in Filipino) may be considered a core course that focuses on language and communication. This course is described as “writing, speaking and presenting to different audiences and for various purposes” (CMO 20-2013). In this new course, students are expected to learn language skills taught in three separate subjects in the old curriculum. Since the students are expected to be trained not only in one skill, this new GE course will also expose the students to real-life situations and activities that will polish their skills. Sample activities for this course include:

conversing intelligently on a subject of import, reporting on group work and or assignments, writing and delivering a formal speech, mock interview, designing a curriculum vitae (CV) and resume, writing minutes of meetings and other similar documents, preparing a research or technical paper, and making an audio-visual or web-based presentation. (CMO-20-2013, pp. 13-14)

As stipulated in the CMO No. 20 series of 2013, these combined activities are provided to allow students to practice communication strategies with a clear purpose and audience, directed by the criteria for effective communication and appropriate language.

To ensure that the objectives set for this subject are achieved at the end of the semester, language teachers are strongly recommended to use a variety of teaching

methodologies, such as the use of technological tools and apps. The memo urged teachers to integrate multimedia materials in the language classroom. In short, the teachers were encouraged to be multimodal in their design. Multimodality, which is directly associated with multimedia, could be defined as the incorporation of various media elements (audio, video, graphic, animation, and the likes) into a synchronized communicative experience that results in more benefits for the end users than any one of the media elements can provide individually (Reddi, 2003).

Teachers have myriad choices of technological tools that could assist them in presenting their lessons which often include: PowerPoint presentations, word processing, e-mails, web searches, and videos or movies (Arifah, 2014). Along with this list of technological material options, language teachers are encouraged to venture on the use of digital interactive media in order to project various modes of communication into the classroom.

As Purposive Communication is somewhat recently offered, there are still no known studies on effective strategies, instructional materials, and even assessment methods that would fit this course or any course on language and communication. So, evaluation studies that explore key aspects of language teaching are necessary to acquire a better understanding of efficient strategies of language teachers in various universities.

Key Aspects in Language Teaching

With the amendments to the curriculum in higher education, language teachers experienced conflicts in dealing with the new GE course, as most of the GE courses for language from the old curriculum are already incorporated as core courses in senior high school. The change led to only one GE course for language at the tertiary

level, Purposive Communication. Purposive Communication is an integration of different significant skills for language previously offered in the old curriculum. Also, this course aims to introduce topics or lessons through multimodal materials in response to the need for technology integration in the classroom. Along with these changes, outcomes-based education (OBE) is also introduced as an educational model focusing on student learning outcomes. To plan better the design and delivery of the new language course, curriculum developers, instructional designers, and teachers may best consider previous studies which deal with teaching strategies that focus on three aspects of teaching- instructional materials, teaching strategies, and assessment methods.

Instructional Materials

Different media have long been incorporated into teaching as instructional materials to achieve specific purposes like motivating an interest among the learners; to present information; to provide instruction; and to assess the learning of the students (Fajardo, 2014; Gilakjani, 2012; Kemp & Smellie, 1989; ZHANG, 2016). Instructional materials are essential tools to deliver a language lesson successfully. Aside from the fact that instructional materials provide a reliable platform through which students learn the English language, it also makes teaching and learning a worthwhile activity and creates a meaningful classroom environment (Ghufron et al., 2016). However, the process of selecting instructional materials for classroom use is a challenging task for English language teachers. To find a suitable instructional material to deliver a lesson, a teacher must consider the materials' effectiveness, relevance, and stimulative features (Enokuha et al., 2004; Omabe, 2006; Richards, 2005).

According to Richards (2005), effective instructional materials are developed from several factors, including teacher (language proficiency, training and experience, cultural background, and teaching techniques), learners (language learning needs, motivation, and interests), and contextual variables (culture, class size, and classroom conditions) He mentioned that language teachers in their lessons widely use textbooks. However, he suggested that language teachers can still explore a variety of instructional materials, such as workbooks, CDs, cassettes, and videos, which teachers can utilize in teaching different language skills and in creating an enjoyable learning milieu.

In addition, the advancement of technology brought an ample number of technological tools that teachers can explore in teaching language include multimedia, videos, webcasts, video conferencing, digital television, handheld technologies (like mobile phones, tablets, and iPad), and wireless technologies (the Internet) (Marshall, 2002).

Multimedia materials that teachers often utilize in the language classroom are videos which include movies, music videos, video talks from lecture series or conferences, television shows or advertisements; multimedia presentations like PowerPoint presentations, digital flipcharts, and Interactive Whiteboards; websites such as educational links or webpages, e-magazines, and e-newspapers; computer programs like mobile or computer games and software; and internet platforms, including emails and blogs/vlogs (Grzeszczyk, 2016).

Pedagogical Strategies in the Language Classroom

Teachers can employ a variety of teaching strategies that they can use for classroom instruction. These strategies aid in better attaining the lesson objectives.

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These strategies may be classified as teacher-centered, learner-centered, content-focused, and participative (Makokha & Ongwae, 2001). Teacher-centered strategies often consider the teacher /instructor as an authority. In this type of strategy, the learners are presumed to be passive recipients of knowledge and information from the teacher (Makokha & Ongwae , 2001). In learner-centered strategies, the teacher plays a dual role as a teacher and learner. Since the teacher is considered as a resource rather than an authority, the learners are actively participating in the learning process. (Stenhouse, n.d.) For content-focused strategies, both the teacher and learners could not make any alteration to the topic, as it is sacrosanct (Makokha & Ongwae, 2001). The last type of teaching strategy is participative or interactive. This strategy is driven by a situational analysis requiring both teachers and learners to perform appropriate actions in response to a specific situation. This strategy often incorporates a bit from the other three teaching strategies: teacher-centered, learner-centered, and content-focused, with teaching methods such as lecture, discussion, programmed instruction, study assignment, tutorial, seminar, demonstration, buzz group, role plays, and brainstorming (Makokha & Ongwae, 2001). Makokha and Ongwae (2001) further described these methods in their study, with the lecture method treated as an oral presentation of a teacher (formal or semi-formal) in order to present facts or to explain a particular topic; the discussion method as a dialogue between the teacher and students about a subject matter in order to come up with ideas that would help attain the instructional objectives; programmed instruction as a method of teaching oneself; the study assignment method where the teacher provides reading assignments such as articles, books, research papers, or web pages in advance; the tutorial as a one-on-one teaching method between a teacher and a particular student, and the seminar

where a teacher provides a tutorial session to a group of learners. Makokha and Ongwae (2001) also included the demonstration method, which allows the teacher to perform a specific task to illustrate to the students what specific task to do, how to do it, when to do it, and why there is a need to do it; Buzz group as a method where a teacher groups the students in order to express their ideas and opinions of a subject; role play as a unique strategy that allows students to experience real-life scenarios; and lastly, brainstorming as a means to discover new ideas by giving equal weight to all ideas presented by students. Teachers can either use one or a combination of two or more strategies that could fit the delivery of a lesson.

Aside from Makokha and Ongwae (2001), several researchers and scholars have explored the field of language teaching strategies and techniques to know its effectiveness and appropriateness for the learners (Habok & Magyar, 2018; Intarapanich, 2013; Okmen & Kilic, 2016; Qing -xue & Jin-fang, 2007; Renau, 2016; Thomson, 2012) and they have emphasized that knowing what and how to implement suitable strategies for both teaching and learning a language is essential to ensure the acquisition and proficiency of language skills . This seemingly simple recommendation becomes all the more crucial in today's language classroom where teachers make use of technology as a form of teaching innovation and a way to help students become globally competitive. By helping the students develop the necessary language skills, teachers incorporate technology either to motivate, to deepen or assess the language learning of the students. In the study conducted by Noviyenti (2018), for example, the research participants cited a number of language learning strategies that they were trained to adopt to improve their speaking skills. These strategies include using newly acquired vocabulary in conversations, listening to English conversations, and

watching English movies or shows on television, all of which alluded to the teachers employing multimodal strategies. A number of research participants indicated that their exposure to movies in the classroom exposed them to authentic use of the language, which they also enjoyed. They claimed that to make use of their free time while improving their speaking skills, they also watch movies at home or with friends.

Apart from using a variety of multimedia meaningfully to help the students learn, one of the best practices that English teachers could apply inside their classrooms is to create a positive atmosphere for reading, writing, and learning. Whitaker (2005) mentioned that creating an inviting classroom is an effective strategy to stimulate reading and writing skills development and enhancement. He elaborated that it can be addressed by involving students' senses and emotions, especially by incorporating music, painting, and other art forms. It is easy to grasp the students' attention, and they are often at ease through this strategy.

Assessment Methods

One way to measure the learners' progress in acquiring language skills is through assessment. Amua-Sekyi (2016) defined "assessment as the activities carried out by teachers or by the students in evaluating themselves, which deliver information that can be used as feedback to alter or improve the teaching and learning activities in which they are involved "(p.1).

Taylor and Nolen (2008) provided four assessment activities: events, tools, processes, and decisions. When teachers organize a speech activity or a listening task, assessment events are used. Also, this assessment can be used when teachers let students simulate certain significant events. Assessment tools are used in the language classroom when teachers test students' reading comprehension by

providing a quiz after a passage. In addition, teachers often use assessment processes to ensure that students focus and understand the requirements of a given task (Black & William, 1998). Hence, assessment decisions are utilized to reflect the results of a given assessment.

English teachers must consider the factors mentioned to deliver the lessons better. So, with the current change of curriculum at the tertiary level, it is necessary that English teachers should make use of his/her creativity, knowledge, and skills in developing effective strategies for teaching the new general education course for language and communication, Purposive Communication.

As teachers need to consider developing essential 21st century skills of learners (in addition to addressing the objectives of the courses they are teaching), it is suitable to understand the use of technology as a tool in the classroom. As there are prior positive reactions on technology integration, it would be pertinent to consider previous studies on the use of technology in the classroom.

Technology as a Tool in the Classroom

Acquiring knowledge on effective teaching strategies, apropos instructional materials, and apt assessment methods would not be complete without understanding the significance of technology in the classroom (Okijie et al., 2006). For the past decades, technology has been a reliable aid for teachers in delivering lessons and a dependable support in comprehending lessons among students. It provides multitudinous opportunities to improve instruction quality and learn across content areas. Technological tools are even considered vital in enhancing the necessary skills of 21st century learners.

Technology integration is technically defined as “the point to which technology is utilized to facilitate learning and teaching” (NCES, 2002, p.75) (i.e., it is not simply the use of technology in the classroom, but how technology is effectively used to support teaching and learning) (Torsani, 2016). There are a number of studies which proved that technology integration boosted the quality of lesson delivery and learning outcomes (Celik, 2013; Eady & Lockyer, 2013; Gilakjani, 2017; Li, 2014; Marek, 2014; Trace et al., 2018).

Integrating technology in the classroom has brought changes to teaching methods and learning strategies. Ahmadi (2018) claimed that using technology supports learners in learning based on their interests, which may mean that learners are becoming more responsible for their learning (Lam & Lawrence, 2002). Learners become more independent as they can access limitless information their teacher cannot provide (Gilakjani, 2017). Technology also brought changes to teaching methods (Gilakjani, 2013). Since contemporary learners are considered digital natives, teachers need to be knowledgeable about technological tools and how to use these tools to deliver lessons effectively (Solanki & Shyamlee, 2012). So, to provide meaningful learning, teachers need to maximize learning through technology-based teaching.

These affordances of technology were also observed in the Philippine classrooms. The study of Gorra and Bhati (2016), which explored how the students perceived technology use in the classroom, found that students were more engaged and had positive perceptions of using technology in learning. In addition, the use of computer-based technology in instruction was explored in the study of Paje et al. (2021). The study revealed that the use of computer-based technology in instruction

improved the participants' teaching, uplifting the interests of the learners and their comprehension of the concepts. The study further found that some teachers opted not to use technology in teaching because of some difficulties low ICT literacy, power interruption, unstable internet connection, and lack of facilities (Paje et al., 2021).

Technology has been proven to aid in addressing the different essential needs and aspects in order to meaningfully deliver lessons across content areas (Schindler et al., 2017; Carstens et al., 2021). Specifically, there are also scholar and researchers who explored how technology could enhance language teaching and learning (Chinnery, 2006; Conroy, 2010; Good & Jarvenin, 2007; Ketsman, 2012; Levine et al., 2000; Ramchandran, 2004).

Technology and Language Teaching

The use of technology in the language classroom has become the focus of most recent scholarly research in the field of language pedagogy. Most of these research studies proved that technology integration significantly impacted the students' language learning (Chinnery, 2006; Conroy, 2010; Good & Jarvenin, 2007; Ketsman, 2012; Levine et al., 2000; Ramchandran, 2004). Levine et al. (2000) found that computers can aid learners in enhancing their reading skills, and Ramchandran's (2004) study found that computer-based teaching can help students improve their writing skills. Ramchandran's (2004) findings are consistent with other studies showing that integrating resources from the internet and adopting Google-Assisted Language Learning (GALL) approaches are practical language activities that can assist learners in enhancing their writing skills (Amin, 2020; Conroy, 2010; Strasma, 2010; Abdelmalak, 2015). Aside from GALL-related studies, Chinnery (2006) proved that Mobile-Assisted Language Learning (MALL) had many uses for language

learning. Aside from its accessibility among students, mobile technologies are also less expensive than computers.

As there are developments in technology-based educational materials, language teachers can resort to ample technology options that can be utilized in teaching, especially in a blended learning environment. Shadieff and Wang (2022) identified eight technologies (with different functions) commonly used in today's classroom which include collaborative tools (e.g., Google Docs or Padlets), social tools (e.g., Facebook or Skype), creative tools (e.g., Photo Story or Adobe Spark), learning management system (e.g., Moodle), classroom interaction tools (e.g., Quizlet or Kahoot), multimedia materials (e.g., video or audio resources), presentation tools (e.g., PowerPoint), and wearable devices (e.g., Google Glass). These technological tools support language learning based on their functions. These were proven to facilitate learning and 21st century skills (Shadieff and Wang, 2022).

These researches ascertained that using technology to enhance language teaching and learning is limitless. Language teachers can now resort to technology-enhanced instruction, which includes using movies to teach language skills. Ketsman (2012) confirmed that incorporating technology-enhanced multimedia instruction in a foreign language classroom could make a difference in the progress of the learners' language skills. The study, which used mixed methods, signified that consistent application of technology-enhanced multimedia instruction could aid students to learn and practice considerable language skills.

Indeed, language teachers have to adapt to the rising advancement of technology to attain success in enhancing language skills and the learners' creative and critical thinking skills. As most of the studies show that technology could make a

positive impact on the language skills of students. Technology, like the use of movies, does not only provide a sophisticated presentation of the lessons, but it also makes a more interactive and enjoyable learning experience (Ismaili, 2013; Kusumarasdyati, 2004; Lou, 2004; Xhemaili, 2013).

In contrast to the positive effects of technology on language learning, some researchers stated that extensive technology exposure, like multimedia use, leads to the danger of learners being too spoon-fed with information; thus, they could not process knowledge on their own (Schmid, 2008).

In addition, it could also provide serious problems, especially in relation to the learners' social, physical, and mental health (Sarwar, 2017; Soltan, 2016). Learners frequently exposed to technology tend to experience physical inactivity, leading to obesity, painful wrists, problems with vision, hearing loss, neck strain, and stress (Soltan, 2016). In addition, learners using technology often become isolated, making it difficult to develop strong social skills. Since the learners are often isolated, they often become easily depressed. Additionally, too much exposure to technology distracts the learner from engaging with the lessons or performing their everyday tasks. In other words, frequent use of technology could lead students to lose their sense of focus (Soltan, 2016).

Hence, teachers have a significant role in the success of technology integration in the language classroom, as they often make major decisions on how to teach the lessons. Therefore, their knowledge about technology's usefulness and drawbacks and their creativity to incorporate it in language teaching are necessary.

Moreover, knowledge of how technology is integrated into the classroom is not enough without understanding the characteristics and usage of various technological

tools. One of which is multimedia resources, which have been extensively used in contemporary language classrooms.

Multimedia Materials in the Language Classroom

As technology has been widely exploited in the language classroom, language teachers ventured into using multimedia materials as supplementary tools in teaching. Multimedia materials are recently considered efficient technological tools that can be used in language teaching.

Curtis (2007) stated that exposure to local themes, natural discourse, and cultural information are good opportunities that movies can offer to learners. Multimedia materials like movies can provide entertainment while providing opportunities to learn. It aids students to be motivated and, at the same time, advantageous in second language teaching (Goldstein & Driver, 2014). Mishan (2004) also mentioned that movies could support language teaching because of their authentic nature, their input, and the options they offer for various learners with different learning strategies.

Students are stimulated to develop a resourceful approach to learning because of the use of instructional materials presented in diverse modes (Grzeszczyk, 2016). In addition, Multimedia instructional materials also provide a more accommodating learning scenario, maximize practice for the four basic language skills, and motivate students to participate during class activities (Pun, 2013). Moreover, Fajardo (2014) conducted an in-depth analysis of the specific multimedia-assisted instruction in English used by college instructors, the extent of use of these materials, and the degree of use for the development of language skills. The findings indicated that instructors were applying readily available multimedia materials on their campuses

and they frequently integrate multimedia-assisted instruction to develop the English skills of the learners.

Abdulrahaman et al. (2020) reviewed research articles on using multimedia materials in the classroom. The review showed that multimedia materials developed using different technologies and multimedia components have enhanced teaching and learning over the years. In addition, the review aided in categorizing multimedia materials into web-based and standalone. The standalone multimedia materials are “a category of teaching and learning tools which are not delivered or used over the internet; these are designed to be loaded, installed, copied, and used in the teachers’ or students’ laptops, PCs or workstations” (Abdulrahaman et al., 2020, p. 11). Standalone multimedia materials are proven to be helpful in places with limited access to the internet. An example of this type of multimedia material is Microsoft PowerPoint. While the web-based category is “presented using web authoring tools and is usually delivered online for educational purposes” (Abdulrahaman et al., 2020, p. 11). Web-based multimedia materials are easier to update and deploy than standalone multimedia materials; however, these tools require a stable internet connection. The use of educational videos on YouTube (Shoufan, 2019) and graphic web-based application (Bansagi & Rodgers, 2018) are some examples of this category.

Furthermore, some researchers argued that learning should not be bound by the content nor the design of the content only but should also include how these contents were presented and how the design or multimedia resources were used (Downes, 2005). This shift of focus aimed to enhance possible outcomes. In support of the notion of giving more weight to integrating multimedia resources in the classroom, Laurillard (1993) claimed that it is significant to understand what kind of

role various media play to foster students' learning. Laurillard (2002) later classified media forms into narrative, interactive, communicative, adaptive, and productive. According to Laurillard (2002), these media types support different types of learning, which include: acquisition, investigation, discussion, practice, collaboration, and production. Understanding the different media forms is necessary in order to achieve the optimum use of various multimedia resources. The first forms are the narrative media forms, typically linear and non-interactive (Brown, 2007). These media types present something to the learners, such as texts, images, and videos (Conole & Fill, 2005). The second forms are the interactive media forms that permit learners to explore nonlinearly (Brown, 2007). These media forms respond in a restricted way to what learners do. Web search engines are an example of an interactive media form (Conole & Fill, 2005). The third forms are the communicative media forms which facilitate exchanges between people (e.g., emails, discussion forums), while the fourth, adaptive media forms, refer to any multimedia resources and tools which may change based on learners' actions or responses, such as simulations, virtual worlds (Conole & Fill, 2005). The fifth forms are productive media, which allow learners to produce something mainly through technological programs and tools such as word processors and spreadsheets (Conole & Fill, 2005; Laurillard, 2002).

These studies proved that understanding multimedia materials, their types, and the parts it plays in the classroom is significant to know how it supports learning.

The use of multimedia materials in the language classroom offers numerous benefits to language learners. Based on some studies, multimedia materials have a positive impact on language learning which include: provide authenticity, increase motivation, develop cultural awareness, and enhance language skills of the learners

(Dong and Li, 2011; Eken, 2003; Grzeszczyk, 2016; Keene, 2006; Kusumarasdyati, 2004; Pun, 2013).

Authenticity

According to Seferoglu (2008), one of the best ways to acquire a language is to expose the learners to authentic materials. Multimedia materials present the natural use of language in typical day-to-day situations; thus, these technological tools can be considered authentic (Ruusunen, 2011; Tang, 2011). These materials may develop the learners' linguistic skills with their exposure to standard sentences used in actual interactions and idioms and collocations (Boxer & Pickering, 1995 in Ruusunen, 2011; Grzeszczyk, 2016). With it, learners encountered a detailed account of the rules of speaking the target language, thus raising their pragmalinguistic awareness, which refers to the speakers' know-how of the structure of the language itself (Oxford Dictionary, 2018). In addition, as an excellent example of multimedia, movies illustrate how people manage a conversation and appropriate discourse strategies like turn-taking in actual dialogue. Moreover, multimedia used in the language classroom is often designed to suit the needs of the students. Consequently, these features of multimedia materials certainly aid in improving the discourse competence, the ability to comprehend and come up with a range of spoken, written, and visual texts that are significant features of a language (Stewart, 2006) of the learners (Boxer & Pickering, 1995 in Ruusunen, 2011).

Motivation

Another positive effect that multimedia materials could provide to learners is motivation. Motivation can be simplified as students' interest, excitement, and enthusiasm to learn a target language. Second or foreign language learners should

be motivated enough to be stimulated in challenging assignments as there are many features to consider in mastering a target language well (Mohanty,n.d.).

Motivation plays an essential role in language teaching. Aside from the fact that it is significant to capture the learners' interests, just enough for them to want to participate in the learning process, motivation is also essential to be developed among learners to have an ardent desire for continuous learning. Providing appropriate motivational tools to the learners is substantial to grab hold of the learners' attention for learning. Most recent research studies show that nearly all contemporary learners are inclined to audio-visual materials (Abukhattala, 2016; Haghverdi & Abdpur,2013; Ismaili, 2013; Khan, 2015; Lin,2002). Most of these studies prove that learners' attention is often captured instantly by colorful, entertaining, fun-filled learning instructional materials (Abukhattala, 2016; Zhen, 2016). Learners are easily motivated to listen and participate if presented with stimulating materials like movies and multimedia, enhancing their performance (Khan, 2015; Pun, 2013; Zhen, 2016).

Lin (2002) argued that motivation is the most credible reason for using multimedia materials like movies in the language classroom. The entertainment factor of most movies, and the interactive and vivid qualities of multimedia tools are strongly present, thus Mishan (2004) added that in language teaching, the learning process can become more entertaining, more amusing, and even more straightforward through the use of varied multimedia materials.

Cultural Awareness

Understanding various cultures across the globe is another significant impact multimedia materials could provide to learners. Most authors state that culture is inseparable from language (Hinkel, 1999; Kramsch, 1993 in Parisi & Andon,2016),

which implies that one has to learn the culture of English-speaking countries, to be able to master the English language. It is significant to learn the culture of the target country since it aids the learners in understanding better the kind of traditions and habits that people of a particular country do and its impact on how the target language is used (Ruusunen, 2011).

Aside from the fact that multimedia materials provide a clear picture of the target culture better than any course books, they also illustrate how aspects of non-verbal communication in different cultures works through visual cues (Parisi & Andon, 2016). Through multimedia materials, learners can closely observe how people from different cultures interact in different situations. So, they could infer how culture impacts the paralanguage elements of the target language. With it, they become more aware of body movements, facial expressions, proxemics, and other paralanguage elements are culture-specific and are sometimes not discussed in course books (Parisi & Andon, 2016).

Learners attained intercultural communicative competence if they were taught to compare foreign cultures with their own local culture (Mishan, 2005). Along with it, they must be trained to be culturally sensitive for them to be able to be aware of the cultural message.

Hence, the inclusion of teaching culture in English classes is vital to support language learning. However, most course books narrow down the idea of English culture to major English-speaking countries like the USA and the United Kingdom (Ruusunen, 2011). So, the use of authentic materials like movies would be the best options that English teachers can use to explore other English-speaking cultures like Australia, African countries, and Asian countries like India, the Philippines, Singapore,

etc.. As Sherman (2003) mentioned that film and other multimedia materials are windows on English language culture, it can be a vivid source of foreign culture experience for learners.

Multimedia Materials as Tools in Enhancing Different Language Skills

Tang (2011) elaborated on the efficiency of using multimedia materials in teaching different language skills. Multimedia materials are multipurpose tools for language teaching that can be utilized in discussing many different aspects of the target language (Grzeszczyk, 2016; Ruusunen, 2011). The different language skills that can be developed through the use of movies as a supplementary tool, include speaking skills (Hedge,2000; Katchen, 2003; Khan,2015; Martín & Jaén,2009), writing skills (Baratta & Jones, 2008; Flowerdew & Miller, 2005; Hedge,2000; Wray,2004), reading skills (Ismaili, 2013; Qiang et al., 2007; Wray,2004; Yuksel & Tanriverdi, 2009;),and listening comprehension skills (Gilakjani & Ahmadi, 2011; Ismaili, 2013; King,2002; Lou, 2004). Studies also proved that other multimedia materials could aid in teaching language skills (Grzeszczyk, 2016; Pun, 2013; Susikaran, 2015; Zhen, 2016).

Multimedia Materials and Listening Comprehension. Listening plays a significant role in our day-to-day communication. This skill comprises almost 50% of our daily interaction (Gilakjani & Ahmadi, 2011; Malicsi, 2005); because of this fact, Malicsi (2005) stated that our learning is deeply rooted in listening. For this reason, good listening comprehension skills are essential in acquiring a target language. Thus, a number of researchers desired to know if enhancing listening comprehension skills can be supported by multimedia materials like the use of movies

(Damronglaohapan & Stevenson,2013; Gilakjani & Ahmadi,2011; Ismaili,2013; King, 2002; Luo,2004; Pun, 2013; Safranjanj,2015; Tang,2011).

Tang (2011) stated that through multimedia, learners became more active interpreters of the actual use of language, thus making them also active listeners. He further elaborated that through multimedia, teachers can design activities that would improve the students' listening skills, which was supported by the study conducted by Pun (2013). Through multimedia, students can receive meaningful information because of ample sharing opportunities where they can interact willingly.

Parisi and Andon (2016) mentioned that film watching is one of the interesting inputs to let the learners exercise their listening skills. Film viewing can aid the students to practice the use of bottom-up and or top-down processes (Hedge, 2000) in comprehending the point of the movie. These strategies help in developing the comprehension skills of the learners, as comprehension is fueled by linguistic information, contextual clues, and prior knowledge.

The illustration of authentic informal conversation is another benefit multimedia materials, especially movies, can provide in developing listening skills. It is a fact that the language in movies is authentic; though the language is developed from scripts, it is not intentionally made for non-native speakers. Through films, students are exposed to a wide array of grammatical structures, colloquial language, distinct speed of delivery, and other features of spoken language (Hedge, 2000). Lou (2004) proved in her study that incorporating DVD movies in classes can improve the students' listening skills. Including nine films in the class curriculum over the entire school year helped the students comprehend class discussions better. It was found that instruction through movies created a motivating learning environment, with the students having

lower anxiety levels. Also, the study of Ismaili (2013) verified that movie watching has a significant effect on the students' listening and communication skills. Her study found that movies indeed aid students' understanding and improve their learning skills. As movies presented language more naturally and showed visual context, it attracted the students' attention.

Multimedia Materials and Speaking Skills. One of the major obstructions of learners in enhancing their oral fluency in the English language is the lack of exposure to real-life interactions and the lack of avenues to practice their oral skills (Khan, 2015). Textbooks typically could not answer these needs since they could not even teach instant talks and conversational interactions (Katchen, 2003).

Multimedia materials can provide an excellent opportunity for learners to practice their speaking skills. Dong and Li (2011) mentioned that teachers could explore a great number of activities and exercises that can be utilized in teaching speaking. Teachers can even use software or podcasts to perform mechanical and interactive repeated exercises designed for them (Dong & Li, 2011).

Teachers can also resort to multimedia materials like movies to aid the learners in developing this language skill. In an experiment performed by Lin (2002), they were able to discover that the experimental group who utilized DVD films as a teaching resource in learning oral skills outperformed the results of the control group who did not employ movies. This finding was supported in the study conducted by Seferoglu (2008). Their study discovered that films could provide a wide array of pedagogical options for developing oral skills. The participants of his study unanimously agreed that film viewing provided them numerous opportunities that enhanced their oral skills, which include how to initiate and sustain a conversational exchange; how to

negotiate meaning; how to deal with the different types of exclamation; how to fill in expressions in a conversation; and how to manage colloquial English in real-life contexts. In addition, the participants also mentioned that through movies, they were exposed to a wide variety of speakers, each with their slang, accents, and dialects. Exposure to authentic cross-cultural information and contextualized vocabulary expressions were also among the features of the movies that the participants appreciated. Martín and Jaén's research (2009) also proved that the conversational language skills of the learners could be enhanced through movies.

Moreover, movies can act as a springboard in creating activities that allow students to practice their oral language skills. Tasks that would focus on the speaking skills of the students could be initiated from movies like debate, re-acting a scene from the film or developing an act for an alternative ending to the film (Ruusunen, 2011; Hedge, 2000). With it, class activities are contextualized, and crafting accuracy-based activities becomes meaningful.

Multimedia Materials and Writing. As one of the active skills, writing needs to be practiced flexibly, so that learners can develop fluency (Katchen, 2003). However, teachers are often very mindful of the various features that should be considered in writing, including vocabulary, grammar, syntax, mechanics, coherence, and organization (Gebhard, 1996 in Ruusunen, 2011). Along with it, looking for a stimulating topic, establishing a tone, dealing with the audience and purpose, and discovering meaning are essential factors that must be contemplated in writing (Ruusunen, 2011). Thus, writing classes usually become repetitive and boring. So, to incite the students, teachers can delve into multimedia materials like videos and movies to bring vibrancy to the writing tasks.

Through movies, teachers can train the learners on how to begin with their writing by inculcating prewriting activities; for instance, the teacher can let the students write their assumptions of the movie based on its title. Also, teachers can include prewriting tasks like brainstorming, clustering, free writing, listing, and information gathering to exercise the students' writing abilities. Aside from the prewriting tasks, movies can also aid the students in rehearsing the writing process. Barrata and Jones (2008) found out that movies can help enhance students' academic writing skills. Since movies could provide relevant information (Hedge, 2000), supply vocabulary (King, 2002; Wray, 2004), and model diverse syntactic and semantic use (Flowerdew & Miller, 2005); teachers could develop writing tasks that are good opportunities for students to enhance their writing abilities. These tasks may include writing a film review, providing an alternative ending, writing a letter to one of the film's characters, and writing a synopsis (Parisi & Andon, 2016; Ruusunen, 2011). These activities are expected to test the students' comprehension of the film, aid students on how to express their views through writing, and let them showcase their creativity (Parisi & Andon, 2016).

Through multimedia, writing activities and exercises became more collaborative (Susikaran, 2015). In the study conducted by Tang (2011), multimedia platforms like chat rooms, email, and blogs were explored to teach writing skills. It was found that with the use of those multimedia, writing tasks became more interactive and meaningful. Aside from it, students became more expressive and were not bound to write about a single topic; instead, they could deal with topics in which they were more interested in.

Multimedia Materials and Reading. Like listening, reading is also a receptive skill. Comprehension is also the key to enhancing this skill better. However, most students are not strategic enough to comprehend reading material. So, teachers can assist the learners in developing their reading strategies by including multimedia materials, especially movies, in their classes (Parisi & Andon, 2016). Through film viewing, teachers can help students apply the bottom-up strategy, wherein they can concentrate on using specific language in the dialogue to absorb the information delivered. Or, teachers may allow the students to make use of top-down strategy, where students have to activate their background knowledge to understand the film's message (Parisi & Andon, 2011). Through it, students can master the strategies in a more fun and enjoyable way, which they can also employ in their reading activities.

Multimedia materials can also cultivate the reading skills of students, like movies. With the presence of different modes in a single instructional material, multimedia use in the language classroom supports students in developing their reading skills faster (Grzeszczyk, 2016). The combination of different media, like pictures and text or animation and text, makes the reading text more attractive and the reading experience more enjoyable for the readers, especially visual learners (Tang, 2011).

A good reader must have visualization (Draper, 2012) to picture or visualize the context's events, characters, narration, story, and words. Movies can also enrich the readers' visualization, which is crucial in comprehension. As defined by scholars, visualization refers to the ability to build mental pictures or images while reading (Ismaili, 2013). Khan (2005) stated that movies are effective language teaching tools since they can provide readers with "visuality," which can facilitate comprehension.

Movies are efficient technological tools that train learners to upgrade their visualization, as it provides audio-visual stimuli.

The study conducted by Ismaili (2013) revealed that movie viewing can facilitate language learning, especially in enhancing learners' reading skills. It is based on the experiment results, wherein the experimental group performed better than the control group. Also, the outcome of the study is grounded on the perceptions of the impact of movie viewing on reading shared by both teachers and students. Furthermore, Hibbing and Rankin-Erickson (2003) suggested the Watch-Read-Watch-Read (W-R-W-R) method in reading, wherein the students build background knowledge of the text, make predictions, watch a segment of the film, read more of the text, confirm understanding, make other predictions, watch more of the movie, and continue reading the material. According to them, it would develop the students' background knowledge and integrate it into their understanding of the concept. To use this method, teachers can look for a movie version of the novel or short story to be read by the class, a movie of the same theme as the reading text, or a movie or video that shares the same concept or topic as the reading material.

As there are a number of observed benefits in integrating technology in the classroom, frameworks or models on technology integration were developed by researchers to understand how technological tools were integrated and can aid in language teaching and learning.

Technology Integration Models

Technology integration in the classroom has long been studied for decades (Shulman, 1987; Hughes, 2002; Mishra & Koehler, 2006; Welsh et al., 2011) to attempt to fully comprehend how technology can be integrated into the classroom in

meaningful ways. With the growing number of studies, a number of integration models were developed and used by different researchers and educators. Three most popular theoretical models or integration models, RAT, TIM, and TPACK, were explored in this study to understand how language teachers integrate technology in the classroom.

Replacement, Amplification and Transformation (RAT) Model

The RAT integration model is the abbreviation for replace, amplify, and transform. Hughes developed this model (2002), originally intended as a self-assessment tool, to understand the nature of technology-supported practices of teachers. This tool was developed in order for teachers to reflect on the effectiveness of the technology they employed in their classrooms. According to Kimmons (2018), this technology integration model claims that in incorporating technology in the classroom, technology is employed “to replace the traditional methods in teaching, to amplify students’ learning, or to transform the learning processes in instances not possible without technology” (Hughes et al., 2006, p.1616). The RAT model can aid in comprehending if a technological tool functions as replacement, amplification, or transformation when used in the classroom (Hughes et al., 2006). Hughes (2002) elaborately defines each category based on how technology is utilized in the classroom. In replacement, technology acts as a digital means, which replaces traditional teaching tools in delivering the same instructional practices. The amplification category “increases efficiency, effectiveness, and productivity of same instructional practices” (Hughes et al., 2006, p.1617). For the transformation category, “technology invents new instruction, learning or curricula” (Hughes et al., 2006, p. 1618). In addition, Hughes et al. (2006) explain that in order to assess the contribution of technology in the classroom, one has to consider

three themes, namely: instructional methods, student learning processes, and curriculum goals, and these themes have more specific dimensions of each.

Some researchers employed the RAT framework as a lens for evaluating technology integration in the classroom. Billingsley et al., (2019) used the RAT model to administer a review on the potential use of immersive virtual reality (VR) in teacher education as a training tool to acquire essential skills like learning concepts. Dang et al., (2012) also used the RAT model to distinguish the affordances of the technology-use purposes of the Learning Management System (LMS). Though, in general, the use of LMS was considered an amplification of typical physical classroom practices, it was found that some specific tools used in LMS were identified as a replacement, and others were marked as an amplification. The use of LMS itself was considered as the transformation. Furthermore, Marcial (2016) conducted a study that employed the RAT model to understand the effectiveness of using social media in teaching in selected Philippine classrooms. In the study, adjustments were made in the framework to present better the descriptions of social media use in the classroom. Replacement is renamed substitution; wherein social media is considered a substitute tool for teaching a lesson. The amplification category highlights the comprehensive integration of social media into teaching and learning. The degree of social media use determines whether or not the practice may be considered under the transformation category. In best-case scenarios, social media can be viewed as a catalyst of change, which aids in redesigning the traditional methods of teaching (Marcial, 2016).

Read (2022) reevaluated the RAT model and its relevance in assessing the use of technology in the contemporary classroom. She mentioned that the RAT framework does not recommend that all technological tools be transformative, nor a certain level

must be attained. Rather, transformative technology is subjective, wherein teachers can either make their lessons transformative or not. She clarified that technology integration must be meaningful, taking into account the positives and drawbacks of its use are well comprehended.

Technology Integration Matrix (TIM) Model

Another framework which can be used to describe and target the use of technology to enhance learning is the Technology Integration Matrix (TIM) model. The TIM framework was developed in 2005 by the Florida Center for Instructional Technology (FCIT). This model is a matrix composed of 25 cells, which are the incorporation of five characteristics of meaningful learning environments, which include the active, collaborative, authentic, and goal-directed, and the five levels of technology integration: entry, adoption, adaptation, infusion, and transformation (FCIT, 2021).

Some researchers employ the TIM framework in assessing technology integration in the classroom. A correlational study was conducted by Barbour (2014) used TIM to assess technology integration and student engagement. The study proved a positive correlation between technology integration and student engagement in the classroom. The study also validated TIM as a potential measure of both levels of technology integration and as an indicator of student engagement (Barbour, 2014). Another study conducted by McKenna et al. (2016) used the TIM framework to assess how Technology Integration Matrix (TIM) influenced the preservice educators' metacognition about technology integration into teaching and learning. The study found out that TIM helped preservice educators increase their awareness of today's learners, ISTE standards, their understanding of pedagogy, and their abilities

to transform learning experiences (McKenna et al., 2016). In addition, a case study conducted by Harris and Yeara (2019) explored the degree of the six first-year teachers' incorporation of technology in their lessons. It was revealed in the study that teachers described active learning situations, and most of the teachers are often in the entry and adoption levels of technology integration.

The FCIT (2021) continuously updates this technology integration model, and a recent third edition was released in 2019. The TIM descriptors are all applicable in face-to-face instruction, as well as online classes.

Technology, Pedagogy, and Content Knowledge (TPACK) as a Technology Integration Model

One of the technology integration models which is applicable in looking at the efficiency of the integration in the classroom is the TPACK (Technology, Pedagogy, and Content Knowledge) model, which Mishra and Koehler developed (2006) based on Shulman's framework (1987 in Mishra & Koehler, 2006).

In this model, there are three main elements of teachers' knowledge: technology, pedagogy, and content. Along with the main elements are the interactions between and among these bodies of knowledge, namely: technological pedagogical knowledge (TPK), technological content knowledge (TCK), pedagogical content knowledge (PCK), and technological pedagogical and content knowledge (TPACK).

The Components of the TPACK model

Content Knowledge. The knowledge of teachers that deals with the subject matter to be learned or taught is called content knowledge (CK) (Mishra & Koehler, 2009). According to Shulman (1986 in Mishra & Koehler, 2009), knowledge of content includes knowledge of concepts, theories, ideas, organizational frameworks,

evidence and proof, and established practices and approaches toward developing such knowledge. Teachers must have a deep understanding of the fundamentals of the discipline in which they teach, for there is a tendency for students to receive incorrect information and develop misconceptions about the content area (Pfundt & Duit, 2000) if teachers are not able to relay a comprehensive base of content knowledge. In the context of the study, the knowledge of teachers on the different language concepts is the scope of this element.

Pedagogical Knowledge. Teachers' deep knowledge about the processes and practices or methods of teaching and learning is called pedagogical knowledge (PK) (Mishra & Koehler, 2009). This knowledge can be utilized to comprehend how students learn, general classroom management skills, lesson planning, and student assessment. PK requires an understanding of the cognitive, social, and developmental theories to find apt techniques or methods in teaching, along with suitable assessments that fit the characteristics of the students. Strategies on how to present the language concepts to the students are to be considered in this item.

Technological Knowledge. Knowledge about technology is said to be complex and dynamic (Ersanli, 2016). Thus, teachers are required to have a constant upgrading of this knowledge. Some authors said there could be no appropriate definition of technological knowledge (TK) at a certain period as it may become outdated in just a month (Mishra & Koehler, 2009). However, when TK is used in TPACK, its definition is close to that of Fluency of Information Technology (FITness), which is proposed by the Committee of Information Technology Literacy of the National Research Council (NRC, 1999 in Mishra & Koehler, 2009). They mentioned that FITness requires a deeper, more essential understanding and mastery of

information technology for information processing, communication, and problem-solving than the traditional definition of computer literacy. Through TK, teachers can finish various tasks utilizing information technology and devise different ways of accomplishing a given chore. With it, TK can be seen as developmental, where technology is considered constantly evolving. The use of multimedia materials in the language classroom is the focus of the teachers' technological knowledge.

Pedagogical Content Knowledge. The pedagogical content knowledge (PCK) in TPACK is comparable to Shulman's (1986 in Mishra & Koehler, 2009) idea of pedagogical knowledge (PK), wherein it deals with knowledge of pedagogy appropriate to the teaching of specific content. Teaching, learning, curriculum, assessment, and reporting (such conditions that advocate learning and the links among curriculum, assessment, and pedagogy) are the common concepts which concern the PCK (Mishra & Koehler, 2009). Teachers' knowledge of how to effectively present the language topics using appropriate pedagogical strategies is this element's primary concern.

Technological Content Knowledge. To develop appropriate technological tools that would suit educational purposes, it is significant that teachers have a deep understanding of technology in the practices and a vast knowledge of a given content area (Mishra & Koehler, 2009). Thus, every teacher must have technological content knowledge (TCK) since TCK is an understanding of how technology and content impact one another. Teachers must be aware that technological options afford and constrain the content ideas that can be discussed. On the other hand, there are also specific content topics that can limit the types of technologies employed. Within this

study, the teacher's ability to use movies and other multimedia tools as a form of technology to present the language topics is the essential point of this element.

Technological Pedagogical Knowledge. Teachers' knowledge of how learning and teaching can be enhanced when technology is employed is called technological pedagogical knowledge (TPK). This type of knowledge deals with how teachers exploit technology in order to deliver their lesson well. TPK, then, requires a teachers' forward-looking, creative, and open-minded use of technology to advance students' learning and understanding (Mishra & Koehler, 2009). For this item, teachers' knowledge on how to make use of movies as a technological tool to deliver the language lessons effectively is an important aspect of this TPACK aspect.

Technological, Pedagogical, and Content Knowledge. The understanding that emerges from the collaborations among the three-core knowledge is called technological pedagogical and content knowledge (TPACK) (Mishra & Koehler, 2009). TPACK is the foundation of effective pedagogy of a particular content topic with technology. This model recommends that each component: content, pedagogy, technology, and teaching/learning contexts have functions to perform individually and as a group (Mishra & Koehler, 2009). So, to teach successfully with technology, teachers must know how to continually create, maintain, and re-establish a dynamic equilibrium among all the components (Mishra & Koehler, 2009).

In addition, The TPACK model presents several possibilities for promoting research in teacher education, teacher professional development, and teachers' use of technology (Mishra & Koehler, 2009). For the past decade, there have been sufficient research studies which try to measure the impact and importance of the collaboration of TPACK in the language classroom. Liu et al. (2014) conducted a study

on developing TPACK in English as a Foreign Language (EFL) teachers. The study discussed four obstacles that hinder teachers from developing TPACK. These include integrating technology into teachers' present knowledge system, the relationship between new and old knowledge, teachers' willingness to accept new technology, and teachers' weaker position in using new technology. So, support to develop EFL teachers' TPACK and suggestions on what specific measures should be taken were provided to aid teachers in enhancing their TPACK. Mahdum (2015) performed a study on the TPACK of in-service senior high school English teachers in Pekanbaru, Indonesia. The study results indicated that the English teachers could develop and apply their TPACK well. Moreover, Ersanli (2016) explored the effectiveness of a five-week workshop and training sessions on TPACK of pre-service English language teachers in Turkey. The findings showed a significant improvement in the TPACK scores of the research participants regardless of their gender. They also performed better in designing and integrating language learning instructional materials with the use of technology. This study supported the results of the study conducted by Tai (2013) on the TPACK-in-Action workshops in English classrooms in Taiwan. The study's findings showed that the TPACK-inAction CALL workshop had an affirmative impact on English teachers. Teachers' perceptions of their TPACK should be considered to assess and evaluate the weak points of integrating knowledge. Kose (2016) investigated the perceptions of English language instructors' TPACK across different levels at different state universities in Turkey. The results indicated that the English instructors believe they are highly competent in the courses they handle. However, they are uncertain if they are proficient enough in technology integration to carry out a sound pedagogy in their content teaching. The findings of this study

supported the earlier claims of previous research in the same field. Recently, a study which employed the TPACK framework was conducted by Morales et al. (2021) in the Philippines. The study explored the technology integration traditions, transitions, and best practices in the classroom. The analysis of the study revealed that the technology integration practices of the teachers, which is associated with the TPACK system, matched the Philippine Professional Standards for Teachers (PPST) domains specific to pedagogy and content, assessment and reporting, and diversity of learners and learning environment (Morales et al., 2021).

The use of technology integration models can aid in assessing elements essential in the meaningful and successful use of technology in the classroom. Moreover, technology integration models provide a perspective to evaluate the effectiveness of technological tools in learning. Also, technological integration models may increase awareness among teachers, like the possibility of challenges in using technological tools in education settings.

Challenges Encountered by Language Teachers in Using Technology

Despite the increasing popularity and growing need to integrate technology in the language classroom, there are research studies which proved that there are challenges encountered by language teachers which often hinder the successful integration of technology Johnson et al. (2016) classified the challenges encountered by English teachers in using technology in their classrooms as external and internal challenges. External challenges include access, training, and support. It was found that the lack or insufficient quantity of technological tools in the institution where teachers are affiliated is one factor that leads to access constraints, thus hindering them from utilizing technology in the classroom (Fisher et al., 1996). Another

external challenge English teachers face is the lack of training related to technology. Even though language teachers are knowledgeable enough about the lesson but lack adequate training on what technological tools and how these tools are to be used, the integration of technology remains unsuccessful (Ertmer et al., 2012).

Another constraint concerns support. The lack of technical, administrative, and peer support often hinders effective technology integration among language teachers (Ertmer, 1999). While the internal challenges include the teachers' attitudes, beliefs, skills, and knowledge. Teachers' perception and attitudes toward educational technology and integrating it into the language classroom is also an obstacle to integrating technology into the classroom (Keengwe et al., 2008; Lowther et al., 2008). Along with it, inadequate skills and knowledge on proper integration of technology obstructs the proper usage of technology in pedagogy (Hughes, 2005).

Johnson et al. (2016) provided a general classification of the challenges often encountered by teachers in integrating technology in the language classroom; however, a more specific classification was earlier observed by van Braak (2001). The categories of challenges pointed out by van Braak (2001) include material and finance, school-specific factors, and human support. The first constraint identified as a major obstacle in using technology in the language classroom is the material and finance. Several studies claimed that limited access to computers and inadequate funding to purchase quality and efficient technological resources were factors which hinder English teachers from different levels of education across the globe from integrating technology into their classrooms (Ashrafzadeh & Sayadian, 2015; Asik et al., 2019; England, 2007; Li, 2014; Yunus, 2007). The second challenge identified is school-specific factors. An example is the school schedule (Bauer & Kenton, 2005;

Becta, 2004; Castillo, 2017; Cleaver, 2014; Dai, 2001; Johnson et al., 2016; Pazilah et al., 2019; Pelgrum, 2001; Rahman, 2015; Sicilia, 2005; Singh, 2019; Tang, 2011; Toprakci, 2006; Wang & Han, 2011; Yunus, 2007; Yunus et al., 2009). Becta (2004) and Sicilia (2005) found that teachers often lacked time to plan lessons that integrate technology, look for appropriate technological materials, and set up classroom tools. A few studies noted that most of their teacher-participants admitted that the duration of a typical class was insufficient to integrate technology into their lessons (Hedayati & Maramdi, 2014; Raman & Yamat, 2014). Other factors also come into the picture; for instance, when the internet connection is unstable, uploading materials takes a while, and the software cannot load. These observations were supported by the study of Yunus (2007), which showed that language teachers often limit the use of technology due to limited class hours. The third challenge identified is the human factor; this constraint is often the teachers' beliefs and attitudes towards technology use in the language classroom (Johnson et al., 2016; Mumtaz, 2000; Pazilah et al., 2019; Rahman, 2015; Van Praag & Sanchez, 2015; Yunus et al., 2009). If teachers tend to have a lack of willingness to integrate technology due to insufficient insights into the positive possibilities that technology integration can provide, the goal of employing technology is often unsuccessful (van Braak, 2001). Along with it, teachers' and students' lack of interest in innovative teaching and learning is one of the key factors which might affect the integration of technology in the language classroom (van Braak, 2001). The fourth challenge is support. Studies have shown that lack of external support (e.g., technical, and training) is also an obstacle experienced by language teachers in integrating technology (Aydin, 2013; England, 2007; Hedayati & Marandi, 2014; Tang, 2011; Yang & Huang, 2008; Yunus, 2007).

Often, teachers are discouraged from employing technology in the language classroom due to a lack of external support (van Braak, 2001). Tang (2011) also stated that using multimedia materials in teaching was sometimes interrupted due to some issues with high-technology materials, and teachers often received no technical support. Thus, they opted to limit the use of technology in teaching their lessons.

Despite the increasing research studies on the challenges encountered by teachers using technology in the language classroom, there is still a limited literature for this topic in the Asian context, especially in the Philippines. Thus, this study also explored the challenges experienced by language teachers in using technology, specifically multimedia materials, aside from examining the perceptions and practices of the language teachers.

Solutions Employed to Address the Challenges

As of today, there are no known established solutions to the identified challenges in using technology in the classroom since most challenges are unique to every teacher and to every school. However, researchers, practitioners, and teachers had proposed possible solutions to the common challenges encountered by the teachers in utilizing technology (Bingimlas, 2009; Fajardo, 2014; Gilakjani, 2012; Johnson et al., 2016; ZHANG, 2016).

The common suggestions to address material and financial constraints are to provide ICT resources, both software and hardware, by augmenting the budget for ICT (Fajardo, 2014); to encourage instructors to utilize readily available resources to maximize the tools acquired by the institutions; (Bingimlas, 2009) and to obtain funds through non-traditional ways like looking for grants from private organizations or crowdfunding from stakeholders (Johnson et al., 2016).

The recommendations provided for the school-specific challenges are to provide sufficient time for lesson preparation (Gilakjani, 2012); and to lessen the number of lessons to be delivered (Bingimlas, 2009). Also, teachers tried to come to class early so that they have ample time to set up the technological materials needed for their lesson.

Moreover, the propositions formulated to deal with human constraints are to provide training regarding new pedagogical approaches and proper utilization of technology (Bingimlas, 2009; Fajardo, 2014; Gilakjani, 2012; Johnson et al., 2016; ZHANG, 2016) In addition, the suggestions emphasized for the challenges of support are to provide continued technical support (Bingimlas, 2009), and strengthen teacher training on the use of technological tools (ZHANG, 2016).

The effectiveness of the solutions provided are not yet tested; thus, this study also explored the possible solutions applied by the teacher-participants in order to cope with the challenges they faced in using multimedia materials in their classroom.

The Perceptions of Teachers on Technology Integration in the Language Classroom

As teachers perform an essential role in technology integration in the classroom (Neiderhauser & Stoddart, 2001), there are a number of studies which focused on the importance of evaluating and measuring the attitudes and perceptions on the effectiveness of the integration of technology in the language classroom (Almekhlafi & Almeqdadi, 2010; Correos, 2014; Dela Rosa, 2016; Khalid, 2007; Kolbakova, 2014; Saqlain & Mahmood, 2013; Tanveer, 2011).

The perceptions, experiences, and attitudes among novice and expert language teachers on the use of Information and Communication Technologies (ICTs)

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in language teaching were considered in the case study conducted by Dela Rosa (2016). His study revealed that despite the limited know-how of the language teachers, they have positive views of the future of ICTs in language teaching. Some qualitative studies revealed that, despite seeing the potential of ICTs, there are factors that hinder language teachers from integrating technologies into their classes effectively (Correos, 2014; Khalid, 2007; Kolbakova, 2014; Saqlain & Mahmood, 2013; Tanveer, 2011). These factors include a lack of professional development training, motivation, technical problems, and financial support. These studies also provided almost the same implications, which include technology training for language teachers, and provision of state-of-the-art software and hardware products to enable teachers to integrate technology successfully into language teaching.

As shown in the studies, considering teachers' perceptions is a good move. Aside from the fact that it aided in investigating the success of technology integration, it also helped inspect the teachers' views regarding the use of technology in their classrooms. Through it, there was a thorough inspection of the factors that could affect the success of adopting sound pedagogy with technology.

Teachers' Perceptions on the use of Multimedia Materials in Language Teaching

Though using multimedia materials in the language classroom is gaining compliments, some researchers, practitioners, and academicians still doubt the effectiveness of using multimedia materials as support in teaching a language. It is therefore deemed vital to consider the perceptions and attitudes of the persons directly involved in multimedia integration in language classes. It should be done to know the impact of this pedagogical approach on language development.

The teacher perceptions were considered in Ismaili's (2013) experimental study. They claimed that movies could support language learning. However, they mentioned that looking for a suitable movie that would fit their students' level of proficiency would be difficult. This conclusion is also supported by the study by Xhemaili (2013), where perceptions of teacher participants were accumulated. The research participants were also optimistic about the effectiveness of movie viewing in enhancing language skills, especially their reading skills. Also, they mentioned that it is significant to use an apt movie in language teaching. However, teachers claimed one disadvantage of using movies as a teaching tool. They said movie viewing was very time-consuming; it would cover 2-3 sessions, affecting their lessons' flow.

Kabooha (2016) employed a mixed-method research design in her study on the perceptions of teachers on the use of movies as multimedia materials and found that movies are effective pedagogical tools which can aid the learners' language development.

Some studies explored teachers' perceptions of using other multimedia materials in the language classroom. Nachimuthu and Vijakayumari (2012) ventured into the perceptions of college educators on the use of multimedia. They found that the participants' views on multimedia use were not affected by their civil status, sex, and technical skills. Most participants have a positive view of multimedia integration in the classroom. Also, they indicated that multimedia could support teaching language skills. In relation to multimedia, some studies delved into teachers' perceptions of internet use and the resources there as multimedia materials. For instance, the studies of Acikalin (2009) and Aydin and Mclsaac (2004) on the attitudes and perceptions of both in-service and pre-service educators on the use of the internet in the classroom

proved that it could facilitate learning. Most of their respondents favored using the internet as a multimedia tool because of its efficiency in accessing and acquiring relevant and up-to-date information.

However, Schmid (2008) stated that some students have difficulty processing information because of the varied modes present in one instructional material. In this instance, multimedia cannot support language learning but rather make it more complicated, especially for slow learners. Along with it, he emphasized that multimedia materials provide everything, making no room for the learners to think critically.

Most of these studies implied that a deep understanding of a particular trend was attained by inspecting the perceptions and attitudes of the research participants. Therefore, to better understand the effectiveness of using multimedia materials in the language classroom, a profound study of the teachers' practices and perceptions on the use of multimedia materials as language teaching tools must be conducted. Furthermore, to ensure the credibility and validity of the study, it would be better to focus on the teachers, as they are professionals and might not be easily influenced. Also, the teachers' practices and perceptions of multimedia consumption are essential for they are the ones who take control of the technology integration in their lessons.

In addition, there are no known studies yet, particularly in the Philippine context, which investigated the practices and perceptions of English teachers, specifically on the use of multimedia materials in language teaching. Hence, an exploration of the practices and perceptions of English language teachers on using multimedia materials in language teaching is timely and relevant.

Conceptual Framework

Figure 1

Conceptual Framework of the Study

Figure 1 represents the key variables relevant to the study and how they may relate to each other, which can help shed light on how the objectives would be met. In the framework, the English college teachers, with their diverse profiles (including experiences and qualifications), employ varied actual practices on the use of multimedia materials in teaching a communication course and may have different perceptions of the use of multimedia materials. As shown in the diagram, arrows

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link English college teachers to practices and perceptions on the use of multimedia materials.

The practices in teaching a communication course include numerous elements like classroom management, assessments, and teaching strategies. Specifically, this study focuses only on teaching strategies. Hence, other practices in teaching are not part of the concern of this study.

Practices in teaching a communication course and the teachers' perceptions of the use of multimedia materials may directly impact the teaching strategies. Hence, broken arrows link these two variables to teaching strategies. The teaching strategies could be teacher-centered, student-centered, content-focused, or participative. The teacher could integrate multimedia materials as part of their teaching strategies; thus, an arrow links these variables. This integration of technology could be assessed through an integration model. Then, teachers might encounter challenges or obstacles while using technology; hence an arrow links these variables. These challenges could be categorized into material and finance, school-specific, human, and support. In order to deal with the challenges, teachers may employ diverse solutions. The solutions are unique based on contexts like the teacher, school, or situation. As shown in the diagram (Figure 1), an arrow connects this variable to challenges encountered in using multimedia materials. Also, this variable may impact the challenges encountered. Thus, a two-headed arrow was used.

Comprehending the classification of the strategies, integration of technology, challenges encountered in using multimedia materials and the solutions or approaches employed to address the challenges are significant in order to come up

with the research output, which could either be a policy development or curriculum and material enhancement.

Operational Definition of Terms

The following terms are defined in the context of the study:

Perceptions - Adopted from the definition of McDonald (2012), the term refers to "an individual's or group's unique way of viewing a phenomenon that involves the processing of stimuli and incorporates memories and experiences in the process of understanding" (p.3).

Practices - The term refers to the "ways in which teachers understand and implement instruction and generally reflect beliefs and ethics about the teaching and learning process" (Hunter & Rasmussen, 2018, p.366).

Multimedia - adopted from the definition of Pandey (n.d.), the term refers to "a combination of text, audio, still images, animation, video or interactivity content forms. It is usually recorded and played, displayed or accessed by information content processing devices such as computerized and electronic media devices but also as part of a live performance (multimedia)" (pp. 3-4).

Teaching strategies - to avoid confusion between teaching methods and teaching strategies, the researcher adopted the definition of Ayua (2017) for this term.

Teaching strategies are methods and techniques that a teacher uses to support their pupils or students through the learning process; a teacher chooses the teaching strategy most suitable to the topic being studied, the level of expertise of the learner, and the stage in their learning journey (p. 5).

Challenges - Adopted from the definition of Johnson et al. (2016), the term refers to anything that is considered as a barrier to effective use of technology in the classroom.

Solutions - Refers to the alternative ways on how to address obstacles or hindrances met in using technology as part of teaching strategies.

Chapter III

Research Methodology

This chapter focuses on the research methodology used in the study and specifically describes the research participants, sampling method, research locale, research instruments, data collection procedure, data analysis procedure, and ethical considerations of the research.

Research Design

This study used qualitative research to address the study's objectives, which are mainly exploratory (Creswell, 2014). According to Creswell (2009), qualitative research is an organized scientific analysis that seeks to build a holistic, narrative description to inform the researcher's understanding of a social or cultural occurrence. McMillan and Schumacher (1993) defined the qualitative research method as "mainly an inductive process of organizing data into categories and recognizing patterns (relationships) among categories." This definition implies that data can be retrieved only from its natural setting (Creswell, 2014).

Qualitative research serves as a canopy for a broader range of research designs, which differ in focus, assumptions about the nature of knowledge, and the role of the researcher (Creswell, 2007). Specifically, this study used phenomenological research design (Heidegger, 1988; Moustakas, 1994), as it aided the researcher in understanding better the lived practices and perceptions of English language teachers on the use of multimedia materials in teaching a communication course at the tertiary level.

Phenomenological Research

Heidegger (1988) claimed that phenomenological research focuses on the wholeness of experience and the search for the essence of experiences. Phenomenology is mainly built on a well-defined concept of experience (Moustakas, 1994; Cilesiz, 2010), which is the primary inquiry of this study. Cilesiz (2010) identified significant functions that can be realized in educational technology research through phenomenology; one of these functions is “to allow the study of experiences with technology in-depth and in a multifaceted and comprehensive manner.” Considering all these descriptions of phenomenology as a research design, a phenomenological study was deemed a suitable method to investigate practices and experiences on multimedia materials integration in language pedagogy.

Phenomenology can be classified into three major categories which include: Transcendental Phenomenology, Hermeneutic Phenomenology, and Existential Phenomenology (Kafle, 2011). Transcendental phenomenology is the original form of phenomenological study. Husserl (Kafle, 2011; Zahavi, 2003) mentioned that transcendental phenomenology sticks to the idea that experience has to transcend to unveil reality (Zahavi, 2003). Existential phenomenology, on the other hand, is the opposite since this type of phenomenology adheres to describing everyday experiences as perceived by individuals (Kafle, 2011). Hermeneutic phenomenology focuses on the subjective experiences of individuals. This specific school of phenomenology believes that “interpretations are all we have and the description itself is an interpretive process” (Heidegger, 1988).

Van Manen (2003) expressed that hermeneutic phenomenology research in education is not bounded by understanding pedagogy: its description or interpretation.

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It also offers the possibility of pedagogical concerns with students, which could be a means of extracting what is essential. Hence, the appropriate approach for the study is hermeneutic phenomenology since this study focuses on the interpretation of real-life experiences and perceptions of the English teacher on the use of multimedia materials in the classroom.

To gain a good grasp of the research methodology of the study, a table (See Table 1) was provided, which summarized how the research questions were answered by identifying the data needed, the data gathering instrument, and the data analysis procedure.

Table 1

Summary of Research Methodology

Research Questions	Data Needed	Data Gathering Instrument	Data Analysis Procedure
1. What are the strategies used by language teachers in teaching Purposive Communication?	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Teaching strategy/ies used by the language teachers 	Initial Survey, Interview, Class Observation	Descriptive Statistics; Thematic Analysis
2. How do the teachers use or integrate multimedia materials in teaching Purposive Communication?	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Multimedia materials utilized by the language teachers Practices in integrating multimedia materials 	Initial Survey, Interview, Class Observation	Descriptive Statistics; Thematic Analysis
3. How do the teachers address the challenges they face in integrating multimedia materials in teaching Purposive Communication?	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Coping strategies used by language teachers to deal with the challenges 	Initial Survey, Interview, Class Observation	Descriptive Statistics; Thematic Analysis

Participants

The participants recruited for this study are college English teachers from three state universities in Eastern Visayas (Western Leyte and Southern Leyte). The researcher utilized purposive sampling to attain the objectives of the study. This nonprobability sampling method was used since this study was interested in one specific characteristic of the participants, they are college English teachers who were handling the core GE course for language and communication, Purposive Communication, during the study.

Initially, 22 pre-identified English teachers from three state universities qualified to be the study's respondents. However, only 18 college English teachers agreed to participate in the study. Despite the decrease in the number of participants, the sample was sufficient (Ellis, 2016). Though scholars and researchers recommended different sample sizes (Braun & Clarke, 2013; Creswell, 1998; Morse, 1994), Ellis (2016) stated that, in reality, 6- 20 participants are an ample size that could provide experiential information for phenomenological research. Specifically, there were 4 participants from the first institution, with only one female and three males. Out of the 12 teachers who joined the study from the second institution, there were ten females and two males. There were 2 participants from the third institution, one female and one male.

The age of the respondents ranged from 21-57 years old. The length of teaching experience of the participants ranged from 1 month to 19 years.

At the time of the study, CHED implemented a training program for the potential faculty to teach the new GE core courses (CMO 50-2016). The higher education faculty were encouraged to complete the training related to the GE course they were assigned to teach. It was a comprehensive training where all those who accomplished

the required tasks could train other teachers (CMO 50-2016). Among the participants in this research, only one was able to attend the trainers' training for teachers to teach Purposive Communication initiated by CHED.

Some teachers failed to attend or complete the CHED training primarily because of five reasons: (1) some were not yet part/affiliated with the university at the time of the training; (2) there was no proper dissemination of the training opportunity; (3) some have concerns over their employment status; (4) there were scheduling conflicts or the training itself was scarce, and (5) some had a different training assignment (See Table 2 for the cluster theme). The thematic analysis was also adopted (Braun & Clarke, 2006) in coding the reasons of the participants for not attending the training; hence, the first column in the table presented the significant responses until cluster themes were identified.

Table 2

Code Book for Teacher Participants' Reasons for not Attending the Training

Overall Theme: Reasons for not attending the CHED training on teaching Purposive Communication	
Significant Responses	Cluster Theme
<p><i>"the date of the training organized by CHED was prior to the date of my graduation"</i> -Teacher 6</p> <p><i>"I was on study leave for my master's degree"</i> -Teacher 12</p> <p><i>"I am not yet part/affiliated with DLABS when the training started"</i> -Teacher 11</p> <p><i>"I didn't teach Purposive Communication at that semester when the training was held"</i> -Teacher 2</p>	<p>Not yet part/ affiliated to the university at the time of the training</p>
<p><i>"I didn't know that there was one. When they hand me my teaching load it says that I will be teaching Comm. 11, so okay"</i> -Teacher 3</p> <p><i>"not informed"</i> -Teacher 9</p> <p><i>"I was unaware"</i> -Teacher 10</p> <p><i>"Not a reg. faculty"</i> -Teacher 15</p>	<p>No proper dissemination of training opportunity</p> <p>Employment status</p>
<p><i>"There was no training since the day I started teaching the subject"</i> -Teacher 13</p> <p><i>"was assigned to other course training"</i> -Teacher 17</p>	<p>Availability of training/seminar</p> <p>Different training assignment</p>

On the other hand, the other research participants had the chance to attend teaching seminars sponsored by publishing companies promoting their textbooks for Purposive Communication. Around thirty-three percent (33%) of the participants received training, seminars, or workshops on technology integration in the language classroom from other organizations, such as the Philippine Association of Language Teaching, Inc. (PALT, Inc.).

During the study, three participants were fresh graduates; hence, they could not yet receive any faculty training related to teaching the language-related GE course (Purposive Communication). However, these participants were assigned by their department heads to teach Purposive Communication. Even though not all were able to attend the formal training initiated by CHED (CMO 50-2016), it is interesting to know that all participants, including the neophytes, were aware of the course objectives and CHED's goals in implementing the updated GE course, which is to provide the necessary skills for the 21st century learners (CMO 20-2013) based on the data gathered.

The Research Locales

The study was conducted in three state universities in Eastern Visayas. The chosen research locales follow the updated version of the GE curriculum (CMO no.20 s. 2013). In addition, these state universities opted to use English as a medium of instruction; thus, they offered Purposive Communication instead of the Filipino version, Malayuning Komunikasyon. These SUCs are currently leading in the field of agriculture, science, and industrial technology in the region (VSU, 2022; SLSU, 2022; EVSU Ormoc Campus, 2022).

Since these are state-owned universities, their funding sources depend on the National Government (NG) subsidy under the General Appropriations Act (GAA). However, when the government aimed to attain the objectives set by the "Higher Education Modernization Act of 1997", their budget was increased as these state universities and colleges were allowed to utilize their Internally Generated Income (IGP) (Manasan & Revilla, 2015).

With the implementation of free tuition effective August 2017 in higher education, these SUCs limit the number of enrollees per academic year to ensure that the allocated budget is enough to cater to the needs of every student (RA 10931). These state universities imposed a college admission test last academic year, 2018-2019, and only accepted the top 2,500 applicants. As there were a limited number of students, it was expected that the ratio between teacher and students would also be reasonable. The typical, expected class size is only 35 students per section (CMO 52-2007).

Consequently, these SUCs were chosen as research locales for the study because they are committed to upgrading their standard of excellence through ICT integration per the mandate of CHED (CMO 20-2013). Also, these SUCs supposedly have enough budget to acquire essential equipment and facilities like television, Digital Light Processing (DLP), and computers for the implementation of the updated GE curriculum, at least based on their NG subsidy and IGP (VSU, 2022; SLSU, 2022; EVSU Ormoc Campus, 2022); Finally, these universities were taught to have the potential to assist faculty in terms of training and resources (VSU, 2022; SLSU, 2022; EVSU Ormoc Campus, 2022). Table 3 summarizes the resources provided to the faculty of the three state universities.

Table 3*Summary Table for the Provisions Available in each SUC*

	Equipment	Infrastructure	Faculty Support Mechanism
SUC 1	1.Laptop Computer (personal property of the faculty) 2. DLP 3. Personal Computer (office)	1.Computer Laboratory 2.Library (Audio Visual Room)	1.In house training for faculty 2. Wifi connections were provided in the Library
SUC 2	1.Laptop Computer (personal property of the faculty) 2. DLP 3. Television 4. Personal Computer (office)	1.Computer Laboratory 2. Library (Audio Visual Room)	1.In house training for faculty 2.resources (books) 3. Wifi connections in the faculty room
SUC 3	1.Laptop Computer (personal property of the faculty) 2. DLP 3. Television 4. Personal Computer (Office)	1.Computer Laboratory	1.In house training for faculty 2.resources (books) 3. Wifi connections in the faculty room and classroom

The Instruments

The three research instruments used in data gathering for this study were a preliminary survey, class observation, and in-depth one-on-one interviews. These instruments were already used in previous studies and were proven reliable in looking into the study's variables in a natural setting.

Preliminary survey

The preliminary survey utilized for this research was composed of fifteen (15) items (See Appendix B1) that dealt with the background information of the research participants (Allen, 2017). The first ten questions were mainly concerned with the participants' demographics, including general teaching and training experiences in

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higher education (Wright, 2008). The last five (5) items deal with the practices of the language teachers on multimedia materials integration in their classrooms. The items include: the strategies they use in teaching Purposive Communication; use of multimedia materials, strategies in integrating multimedia materials, challenges faced by the teachers in integrating multimedia materials, and solutions in addressing the challenges (Wright, 2008). There are prompt answers for each item based on previous studies (Allen, 2017; Heinz, 2013; Wright,2008). Also, the researcher made it a point that the participants could express their answers not mentioned in the possible answers by providing an option where they could specify their responses (Allen, 2017). Two language experts reviewed the instrument, focusing on language use, to address content validity and face validity concerns (Allen, 2017). In measuring the instrument's content validity, the language experts assessed the comprehensibility of the items in the questionnaire. The language experts also checked if the items were adequate to reflect the practices and perceptions of the teacher participants in using multimedia materials (Morse et al., 2002). In order to ensure the face validity of the instrument, the language experts considered the study's research objectives. They evaluated the relationship of each item to the research objectives (Morse et al., 2002). See Appendix C for the survey instrument.

Class Observation

The researcher also conducted classroom observation. Class observation has many valid and vital educational purposes which can aid in better clarifying answers obtained from other research instruments (Martin, 1977; Meehan et al., 2004). By conducting class observation sessions, the researcher was able to investigate the teaching and learning activities in authentic settings; was able to gain

detailed and precise evidence that could support the other data gathered, and was able to check for any changes, and verify the impact of such changes applied in the classrooms (Waxman, 1995). The researcher used classroom observation notes (See Appendix B2) to perceive the use of multimedia materials through various technologies in the language classroom (Meehan et al., 2004).

The observation focused on the use of technology in relation to the teaching strategies and techniques used by the teacher to deliver the lessons and the assessment activities (Waxman & Huang, 1996). Thus, the researcher performed one to two classroom observation sessions to witness the following: the introduction, the discussion of the topic, and the assessment period (Brevik, 2019). Like the survey instrument, the observation notes were also reviewed by the two language experts in terms of face and content validity. (Waxman & Huang, 1996). The language experts assessed the clarity of the items observed in integrating multimedia materials in the language classroom. Also, the face validity of the items in the observation notes was evaluated based on the research objectives. The language experts ensured that all the necessary parts of the lesson were observed to assess how multimedia materials were integrated (Morse et al., 2002)

In-depth Interview

Another research instrument used for this study was the in-depth interview. The in-depth, one-on-one interview is an appropriate method to collect personal experience descriptions (Kvale, 1996; Simon & Goes, 2013). For this study, the researcher loosely adopted the framework for interviewing provided by Seidman (2006), mainly consisting of open-ended interview questions with each participant. Though semi-structured interview questions were constructed by the

researcher, additional questions related to the responses of the participants in the preliminary survey and class observation were added to deepen and enrich the data needed for the study (Connolly, 2008; Stone, 2016). The language experts also reviewed the guide interview questions, especially on content and face validity (Simon & Goes, 2013). The language experts evaluated the content validity of the interview questions by assuring that each item was clear, logical, and understandable. Along with it, the face validity of the interview questions was evaluated as to how the questions were aligned with the research objectives (Morse et al.,2002).

Data Collection Procedure

As this study employed a qualitative research design, the data collection procedure was guided by the suggestions of Creswell (2013) and Moustakas (1994), along with the ethical guidelines set by the British Educational Research Association (BERA, 2018). The researcher performed five steps in collecting the data for the study, summarized in Figure 2.

Figure 2

Flow Chart of the Data Collection Procedure

Creswell (2013) suggested triangulating the qualitative data from multiple sources, so the data were gathered using three research instruments. Though the flow of the data gathering of this study seemed to follow a sequential explanatory approach, the study remained qualitative. The study remained focused on understanding the lived experiences of the participants. Merriam (1988) and Marshall & Rossman (1989) (in Creswell, 2013) asserted that data collection and analysis need to be nonsimultaneous in qualitative research. Hence, data from the survey was first analyzed, followed by the data from class observation and the interview.

Accordingly, the following steps were performed in collecting the data: preparation/coordination with the research locale, instrument reviews, survey administration, the conduct of class observation, and the conduct of one-on-one interviews.

Preparation/Coordination with the Research Locale

The researcher first sought permission from authorized persons from the three state universities where the study was conducted (See Appendix A1). Then, the researcher provided request letters enclosed with informed consent forms which were personally distributed to the predetermined participants (BERA, 2018; Creswell, 2013) (See Appendix A2). Also, the researcher made pre-arrangements for conducting the class observation sessions and interviews with the participants who agreed to participate in the study (Brevik, 2019; Stone, 2016).

Instrument Reviews

The second step was the instrument reviews. A consultation with the research adviser was performed to ensure that the research instruments constructed were reliable and valid (Creswell, 2013). The research instruments were not pilot tested because of circumstances outside the researcher's control, such as the availability and

willingness of identified participants to join a pilot run. However, the researcher requested two language experts to review the instrument in terms of face validity and content validity (Middleton, 2019).

Survey Administration

The third step was the survey administration. Once all consent forms were collected, the researcher administered the preliminary survey to the participants who agreed to participate in the study (Wright, 2008). After the survey forms were retrieved, the data gathered were processed using descriptive statistics (Creswell, 2013).

Conduct of Class Observation

As the fourth step, the researcher observed the classes of teacher participants who agreed to be part of the class observation. The researcher limited the number of observations to two sessions due to time constraints and participants' willingness; however, the researcher made it a point that the same topic was discussed among the participants during the sessions of observation in order to avoid bias and that the significant parts of the lesson were covered (Brevik, 2019; Waxman & Huang, 1996). The researcher planned to use observation notes and record the sessions (Brevik, 2019). However, most teacher participants declined to have their classes recorded, so the researcher asked permission to take photos instead. So, the data from the class observation only included the observation notes and photos, which were also analyzed before the interview. The data from this instrument aided the researcher in further enhancing the semi-structured questions for the interview, as the researcher aimed to gather more substantial data.

Conduct of One-on-One Interview

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The fifth step was the conduct of the interview. The researcher performed one-on-one interviews with the research participants to gain in-depth information about the topic (McNamara, 1999; Simon & Goes, 2013). The interview questions were drafted based on the framework of Seidman (2006) and refined based on the data gathered through the preliminary survey and classroom observation. After the actual interviews, the researcher analyzed all the data following the hermeneutic cycle, especially the thematic analysis component, to present the results of the study (Braun & Clarke, 2006).

Data Analysis Procedure

Because the study used a hermeneutic phenomenological approach, the hermeneutic cycle was applied in performing the data analysis of the study (Kafle, 2011; Lavery, 2003). The hermeneutic cycle, also referred to as a method of interpretation, involves reading, reflecting, and interpreting data comprehensively, which could mean re-reading the data and starting the cycle again (Kafle, 2011; Lavery, 2003). See Figure 3 for the summary of the hermeneutic cycle.

Figure 3

Hermeneutic Cycle

Note: The image was created from the data analysis of Lavery (2003). From “Hermeneutic phenomenological research simplified” by N. Kafle. *Bodhi: An Interdisciplinary Journal* 5, 2011 (p. 195).

Well-known scholars and researchers (van Manen, 1997; Heidegger, 1988) of hermeneutic phenomenology suggested that there is no fixed method for conducting and analyzing the data for this type of research. Thus, the researcher referred to studies with similar research design and data analysis approach (Walker & Shepard, 2011; Clark, 2013; Lacdo et al., 2018). The data processing and analysis were also realized using the steps in thematic analysis suggested by Braun and Clarke (2006). See Table 4 for the summary of steps performed for thematic analysis.

Table 4*The Summary of Steps Performed for Thematic Analysis*

The Steps of Thematic Analysis	How the Researcher Performed the Step
Familiarizing the Data	The data from preliminary survey and class observation notes were read multiple times and analyzed. Then, the data from the interview were read multiple times and were transferred to the Atlas.ti software for easy data transformation.
Generating Initial Codes	The researcher highlighted significant words or phrases that would describe the experiences of the teacher participants. These were transformed into meaningful units.
Searching and reviewing themes	The researcher recognized significant themes out of the meaningful units identified.
Defining themes	The researcher used the categories identified by the previous studies to classify the themes.
Producing the report	The researcher returned the analyzed data to the teacher participants and asked their confirmation on the meaning assigned by the researcher to their experiences.

As stated, the data from the preliminary survey were first analyzed using descriptive statistics and the data from the class observations were analyzed using thematic analysis. Then, the researcher transcribed the interviews verbatim (Poland, 2002). The researcher merged the data from the interviews with the analysis from other data gathered from the other two research instruments. In doing the thematic analysis, the researcher coded the data based on the suggestions of Braun and Clarke (2006), which include six analytical steps: familiarizing oneself with data, generating initial codes, searching for themes, reviewing themes, defining/naming themes, and producing the report.

Reading

Reading and rereading the data are essential to familiarize it (Laverly, 2003). The researcher ran through the data multiple times and started to generate initial codes (Braun & Clarke, 2006). A preliminary interpretation of the experiences of the research participants regarding the phenomenon studied was performed. Then, the preliminary interpretations were transformed into meaningful units (Clark, 2013).

Reflective Writing

Reflection is necessary for performing analysis in any phenomenological study (Creswell, 2007). Reflective writing describes the nature of a phenomenon based on the participants' experiences as it appears in the consciousness (van Manen, 2007). In this process, the researcher searched and reviewed themes of the extracted meaningful units from the data. In doing so, the researcher often used empathy or a reflection from previous experiences to support interpreting meanings (Sloan & Bowe, 2014).

Interpreting

Hermeneutic phenomenology is interpretive (Heidegger, 1988). To interpret the phenomenon being studied, the researcher did thorough reading and reflective writing, which aided in interpreting the meanings discovered (Sloan & Bowe, 2014). In interpreting the data, the researcher defined themes and produced the report. The researcher utilized the categories identified in the previous studies to organize the themes which emerged from the reflection and interpretation process (Braun & Clarke, 2006; Lacdo et al., 2018) Before finalizing the data analysis report, the researcher consulted the teacher participants regarding troublesome claims from the analyzed

data to ensure that the meanings assigned by the researcher suited and accurately captured the participants' experiences (Clark, 2013).

Ethical Considerations

Guided by conditions set forth by the British Educational Research Association (BERA) (2018), the researcher set responsibilities to the teacher participants, which include: consent, incentives, harm arising from the participation of research, right to withdraw, and privacy.

Consent

As described in the data collection procedure, the researcher first sought permission from the authorities of the research locale. Then, before the study started, the researcher ensured that voluntary informed consent was obtained from the predetermined participants. Also, the participants were free to withdraw their consent at any time they wished for any reason (BERA, 2017). Only English teachers who gave their explicit consent for their participation in the study were part of the administration of the survey, conduct of class observation, and interview (BERA, 2018).

Incentives

Payment for participation in educational research is highly discouraged, as it might impede the participants' will to participate in a research study freely (BERA, 2018; Townsend & Wallace, 2016). With this, the researcher made it clear to the teacher participants that they would not receive any form of compensation for joining the study.

Harm Arising from the Participation of Research

As it is one of the responsibilities of the researcher to manage any distress or discomfort that may arise during the conduct of the study, the researcher considered

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potential risks that may cause emotional or any other harm (BERA, 2018). The researcher made it a point that there were no biases in administering the one-on-one interview, performing the classroom observations, and conducting the survey.

Moreover, the researcher made certain that there was no discrimination towards the participants' abilities and skills during the conduct of the study.

Right to Withdraw

The researcher recognized the right of the participants to withdraw from the study (Zevenbergen, 2016; BERA, 2018). Thus, the participants were informed that they were free to withdraw anytime they were no longer at ease with the conduct of the study (See Appendix A).

Privacy

One of the basic norms of the conduct of a research study is the confidential and anonymous treatment of participants' responses (Townsend & Wallace, 2016). Thus, pseudonyms were used to protect the participants' identities in administering the survey, conducting the interviews, and conducting classroom observation sessions (Sloan & Bowe, 2014). However, some teacher participants initially used their first names or nicknames, so the researcher used numbers as codes (BERA, 2018). In addition, the researcher assured the participants that all the information they disclosed was confidential (Zevenbergen, 2016). Moreover, the researcher willingly answered questions that the participants raised in connection to the study. The researcher promised to provide a copy of the findings of the study to the respondents if they requested it (BERA, 2018).

Chapter IV

Findings and Analysis

This chapter presents the findings from the data gathered and answers to the study's research questions. The researcher analyzes the data through thematic analysis, and the themes which emerged from the analysis acted as a guide in the presentation and discussion of findings and analysis.

Discussion

In the Philippine context, the use of multimedia materials is emphasized by the Commission on Higher Education (CHED) in order to address the needs of the 21st century learners, which include the necessity to cope with the demands of today's globalized world (CMO 20-2013). This study targeted to view the practices and perceptions of the English language teachers on the use of multimedia materials in teaching the updated GE course for language, Purposive Communication as the teachers are the ones who control the implementation of multimedia materials integration in the actual classroom.

In order to smoothly present the findings of the study, the researcher divided the discussion into three main sections, which were based on the overall themes identified during the analysis, namely:

- a. teaching strategies used by the teachers;
- b. the integration of multimedia materials in teaching Purposive Communication; and
- c. challenges encountered in using multimedia materials and actions taken to address these challenges.

Moreover, based on the analysis of the findings, a policy development program on technology integration for teachers was suggested.

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Teaching Strategies Used by the Language Teachers from a Previous Study

As manifested in the data gathered, the teaching strategies used by teacher participants played a significant role in effectively delivering the lessons. As supported by the literature, the success of attaining lesson objectives often relies on the teaching strategy employed (Makokha & Ongwae, 1997). Below is a table summary of the different teaching strategies suggested by Makokha and Ongwae (2001), which became the preliminary basis of the analysis of strategies demonstrated by the teachers in this study (See Table 5).

Table 5

Types of Teaching Strategies

Types of Teaching Strategies	Definition	Sample Strategies
Teacher-centered Strategy	The teacher is considered as the authority in this type of strategy. The learners are passive recipients of knowledge and information. (Makokha & Ongwae, 2001)	-Lecture -Discussion
Learner-centered Strategy	The teacher acts as teacher and learner. The learners actively participate in the learning process. (Makokha & Ongwae, 2001; Stenhouse, n.d.)	-Role Play -Study Assignment -Reporting
Content-centered Strategy	Both the teacher and learners could not make amendments with the topic. (Makokha & Ongwae, 2001)	-Programmed Instruction -Seminar -Tutorial
Participative/Interactive Strategy	Both the teacher and the learners are obligated to respond in a given situation. This strategy employed a bit of the three types of strategies: teacher-centered strategy, learner-centered strategy, and content-centered strategy (Makokha & Ongwae, 2001).	-Demonstration -Buzz Group -Brainstorming -Interactive Lecture -Participatory Discussion

As tabulated in the preliminary survey, the teacher participants indicated lecture and discussion as the most used strategies in presenting lessons in Purposive Communication. In contrast, the least used strategy is the seminar. Interestingly, some teacher participants specified other strategies like using videos, oral participation or presentation, speech writing, and reporting, which were not pre-listed in the survey (See Table 6).

Table 6

Teaching Strategies Used by the Teacher Participants Indicated in the Survey

Type of Teaching Strategies	Number of users	Percentage of Use
Lecture	17	100%
Discussion	16	94.11%
Brainstorming	15	88.24%
Demonstration	14	82.35%
Role play	14	82.35%
Study assignment	12	70.59%
Buzz group	6	35.29%
Programmed instruction	4	23.53%
Tutorial	3	17.65%
Seminar	2	11.76%
Others: Videos		
Speech writing		
Presentation		
Oral Participation		
Reporting		

Teaching Strategy Mostly Used by Teacher Participants. All the teacher participants opted to use lectures in teaching Purposive Communication. As discussed in chapter two, this teaching strategy involves the presentation of facts by the teacher to the learners (Makokha & Ongwae, 2001). The next teaching strategy often used by the teacher participants was discussion, which involves a dialogue between the learners and teachers about a specific topic (Makokha & Ongwae, 2001). Also, the researcher noted during class observation that teacher participants

employed lecture-discussion in delivering the lessons. The researcher noted during class observation that the teacher participants employed discussion, wherein students were called to participate by responding to queries or expressing their ideas about the topic discussed. It was noticed that the strategy enticed participation among the students in the learning process (See Figure 4 and Figure 5).

Figure 4

A Research Participant Using Lecture with Multimedia to Discuss a Topic

Figure 5

A Research Participant in One Lecture-Discussion

The interview responses supported the findings from the survey and class observation; the teacher participants admitted that the strategies they often employed included lecture and discussion due to varied reasons like their beliefs and observation of the students' behavior and responses (McKeachie & Svinicki, 2006). Below are the claims of the teacher participants during the interview regarding the use of lectures and discussions.

"...but most of the time learners will listen kay kung they or attentively if ang teacher gajuy mu-discuss mu-lecture..."

-Teacher 1

(...but most of the time learners will listen attentively if the teacher will discuss or will do the lecture...)

"...because we don't have the technology then let's just have the discussion wherein we can say that during this lectu- ah lectures or discussions it could be monotonous or very boring so I would really let my students use their bodies, use their emotions, and act or get their ideas..."

-Teacher 3

“...if there is meaningful discussion so there is also a meaningful learning to the students.”

-Teacher 4

These findings are analogous to the results of the studies of Eison (2010), Ganyaupfu (2013), and McKeachie and Svinicki (2006), wherein they found that lecture and discussion are popular teaching strategies in higher education. According to Robertson (2013), most teachers in higher education employed lectures as a teaching strategy because it is an effective method to cover much information, especially since there is a limited number of sessions per semester. However, some researchers consider lecture and discussion teacher-entered strategies (See Table 6) (Eison,2010; Ganyaupfu, 2013; McKeachie and Svinicki, 2006) because frequently, the teacher is in control of the presentation of the topic. However, Woodring & Woodring (2011) argued that lectures could be categorized into different specific types, which can also be considered as part or sample of other teaching strategies, like interactive lectures, which belong to the participative teaching strategy (See Table 6). The majority of the teacher participants indicated lecture and discussion as their strategy in teaching Purposive Communication in the survey; however, it was not specified as to the precise type of lecture they utilized. Hence, during class observation, the researcher noted the specific type of lecture employed by the teacher participants, which include multimedia lecture and interactive lecture. According to Major et al. (2015), a multimedia lecture is also known as a slide lecture because of the slide-talk approach, wherein audio-visual materials like Prezi or PowerPoint Presentation are utilized during a lecture session. The researcher observed this type of lecture during the classroom observation (See Figure 5). The utilization of this type

of lecture proved that the teacher participants are aware of the need to integrate multimedia materials in teaching Purposive Communication, as cited in the CMO 20 series of 2013, and the goal to address the need of the 21st century learner by integrating technology (Fajardo, 2014). Also, the researcher noted during class observation that interactive lecture, which is a form of lecturing that includes students in a variety of brief content-related activities in between, like brainstorming (Woodring & Woodring, 2011), was employed by the teacher participants (See Figures 6 and 7). Hence, the teacher participants were also cognizant of the need to employ an interactive type of teaching strategy, which is also essential in developing the communication skills of the learners (CMO 20-2013). In some ways and despite the term, some features of the interactive lecture may complement active learning strategies and techniques that encourage students to discuss among themselves and share something from their ideas to understand the point of the lecture and learn with their peers (Brame, 2016; Carr et al., 2015; Hake, 1998).

Figure 6

The Students during a Brainstorming Activity, which is a Part of an Interactive Lecture

Figure 7

A Brainstorming Activity Performed by the Students as Part of the Interactive Lecture

Teaching Strategy Least Used by the Teacher Participants. While the least used teaching strategy is the seminar, wherein teacher participants provide a tutorial/informal session to discuss a topic with a group of learners (Makokha & Ongwae, 2001). The survey result shows that there were only two teacher participants who made use of this teaching strategy (See Table 5). This teaching strategy was also not observed in any of the sessions. The possible reasons for less utilization of this type of teaching strategy might include: this strategy would give teacher participants additional workload; this is time-consuming, and it is more costly than the other methods (Makokha & Ongwae, 2001).

Other Teaching Strategies Indicated by the Teacher Participants. Remarkably, there were responses by the teacher participants which were not pre-listed in the survey instrument. These included videos and presentations, speech writing, oral participation, and reporting. Specifically, the use of videos, oral participation, and reporting was notable during the class observation. Figures 8, 9, and 10 showcase the application of these strategies in the classroom. The researcher observed that these teaching strategies were appropriate in terms of the lesson, the learners' needs, and the course's objectives (CMO 20-2013; San Jose & Galang, 2015). In support of this claim, Catoto and San Jose (2016) found that oral participation and reporting are effective teaching strategies teachers in the language classroom can use. These strategies are found beneficial as they entice the participation of students in the learning process. Hence it developed their self-confidence, enhanced their communication skills, and honed their hidden talents (Catoto & San Jose, 2016). In addition, the teacher participants also mentioned these details during the interview:

“so naglimit ko to take away the fear factor lang sa, sa in terms of speaking in the classroom, so mao to, mao na to nagreporting nako because I want them to improve sa ilang kaugalingun, sa ilang speaking skills, unsaun nila pagpresent ang ilang self, unsaun nila pagbarog, unsa ila mga gestures na gamitun, mao to etcetera, etcetera...”

--Teacher 6

(So, I limit my strategies just to take the fear in speaking in the classroom, that is why I opted for reporting to help improve my students, their speaking skills, how they will project, stand, and their proper gestures, etc....etc.)

“Yes, yes I allow them to use uh to do reporting. Yeah because I really want them to, to communicate. I always remind them that they would become teachers, and when you teach you really have to talk, and when you talk you talk with- sense, and then when I say sense it involves the presentation of their ideas, the the the pronunciation, which is one of the major problems now among our students.”

-Teacher 16

Figure 8

A Teacher Participant Incorporating a Video Clip During the Discussion

Figure 9

A Student Presenting his Topic during a Reporting Session

Figure 10

An Oral Recitation Session

As the teacher participants are conscious of the course description, they make it a point to integrate multimedia resources to deliver the lessons. Most of them viewed

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technology as a way of addressing the needs of their students who belong to Generation Z who are already considered digital natives (Edutopia, 2007).

Aside from an awareness of the potential significance of using multimedia materials and other technologies, the teacher participants seemed to believe that technology could make the lessons easy, fast, and even entertaining, which is similar to the claims of Whitetaker (2005):

“...like it’s easy to give them activities, uhm like a virtual classroom. And, yes there, some of my students are fond of it...”

-Teacher 1

“...so mas dali man gud mas visual man gud ang mga learners karun maam, so it's very important to we should incorporate multimedia, and it can also of course lessen the burden of kuan kay play nalang nimu diha and everything is given na...”

-Teacher 7

(...so it’s fast since most learners are visual learners ma’am, so it’s very important to incorporate multimedia, which could also lessen the workload of the teachers, as everything is already provided...)

The Integration of Multimedia Materials in Teaching Purposive Communication

Besides knowing and applying appropriate teaching strategies for Purposive Communication, teachers must have ample knowledge about technology, specifically multimedia materials, to deliver the lessons well (Mishra & Koehler, 2006). In other words, properly integrating multimedia materials is vital in teaching Purposive Communication (CMO 20-2013). This theme has two prevailing sub-themes: multimedia materials used by the teacher participants, the integration of multimedia materials, and the technology integration model.

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Multimedia Materials Used by the Teacher Participants. The first sub-theme from the second theme is the multimedia materials used. It was noted from the preliminary survey result that PowerPoint presentation was regularly used by the teacher participants, while the use of interactive whiteboard was never used. Some teacher participants added that they ventured into audio clips and public service announcements as instructional materials in delivering some lessons (See Table 7). Using various multimedia materials, along with other technologies that may go along with the different multimedia types, indicates the desire of the teacher participants to explore various ways to deliver the lessons effectively (Pun, 2013; Zhen, 2016; Samat & Aziz, 2020).

Table 7

Frequency of Use of the Multimedia Materials of the Teacher Participants

Multimedia Materials	Frequency of Use
a) PowerPoint presentations	Regularly
b) Television shows and/or advertisements (clips or full scenes)	Frequently
c) digital flip charts and other infographics	Frequently
d) Entries from educational links or whole webpages	Frequently
e) Excerpts or articles from e-newspapers/ e-magazines	Frequently
f) Blogs (blog entries or sites)	Occasionally
g) Vlogs and or screencasts	Occasionally
h) Video talks from lecture series and /or conferences	Occasionally
i) Music video/s	Occasionally
j) Mobile and /or computer games and/or app	Seldom
k) Movies (either short clips or full)	Seldom
l) Interactive Whiteboard	Never
OTHERS: Audio Clips Public Service Announcements	

Multimedia Material Regularly Used by the Teacher Participants. Using PowerPoint presentations or other presentation programs and web-based creation tools in delivering lessons has long been practiced in higher education (Hashemi et al., 2012). This type of multimedia material is used in place of the traditional teaching materials utilized by teachers (Ho, 2001). It is said that PowerPoint Presentation is commonly used in contemporary language classrooms because it appeals to the learners' diverse learning styles (Oommen, 2012). A number of studies proved that PowerPoint Presentations, or any equivalent, have many advantages when used in the language classroom like increasing students' engagement, reducing students' distraction, helping students to focus on the discussion and enhancing student participation (Szaboa & Hastings, 2000; Brock & Joglekar, 2011; Abdellatif, 2015).

In more recent use of PowerPoint Presentations, teachers often include video clips, animations, and audio to present topics more efficiently, especially when concretizing abstract ideas and trying to catch students' attention (Hashemi et al., 2012). This practice was observed and noted during the class observation. Figures 4, 8, and 14 show the teacher participants using PowerPoint Presentations--a fact that was also emphasized in the interviews. The teacher participants cited that presentations make their discussion easier and provide visual supplements to aid students in comprehending the lessons well. The following are the statements of the teacher participants alluding to these reasons:

"I'm not comfortable doing my lectures without visual presentation, so every lecture naa gyud koy powerpoint so kung di ko magpowerpoint kay mag exercise mi kay basta kay maglecture gani ko about the topic naa gyud nay powerpoint kay dili ko maka explain ug tarung nya I find it very boring pud also mag sige rako ug chika without a atong studyante makit-an na visual impact kay mas maka understand baya na sila if naa silay makita na images, ingana mas, mas maentice sila to listen ingana labi na ug na pa kay mga pashowy showy diha, mga videos, etcetera so it enhance learning, unya facilitate pud siya sa ako part, unya easy for my part no nga ma ensure nako nga in one hour mao ra ni ang points nga gusto ishare sa akong students..."

-Teacher 11

(I am not comfortable doing my lectures without visual presentation, so every lecture I have a PowerPoint presentation, or I will give exercises. I make it a point to use PowerPoint during my lecture so I can explain well. I also find it boring if I will only talk and the students will not see any visual aids since they can understand better if they will see images. They will be more enticing to listen to, especially if you will show videos, etc. so it enhances learning, facilitates my discussion and ensures that I can cover all the topics in an hour because I am guided with the points that I want to share with my students...)

"...sa akong uhm class kay I prepared a powerpoint presentation ang kadtong communication models kay mao man pud ang mura ug para naku, I want them to see jud unta kung unsa ang function, kung unsaun pag- pag travel sa message, etcetera."

-Teacher 6

(...in my uhm, class I prepared a PowerPoint Presentation for the communication models because I want them to see the function and how the message travels, etc.)

Multimedia Material which was Never Used by the Teacher Participants.

The teacher participants responded that they had never used an interactive whiteboard, a tool that can interact directly with a user or with another device using a special pen (Cox, 2019; Davidovich & Yavich, 2017). The reason could be that this technological tool is unavailable in the research locale, as presented in chapter 3. One

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teacher participant also admitted that despite the interest in using this multimedia material, they could not utilize it because the university does not own any.

“...in Europe because I was able to get a scholarship and study there for six months no, sa Czech Republic, so ang ila didto day anindot kaayo ang ila classroom, so you can just- kay ang ila mga teacher inug sud magda ra gyud ug ballpen ug gamay na papel, kay nganu man? in each classroom naa na silay smart na board kana bitawng naay magsuwat ka...

... interactive unya ang ilang projector embedded na, and then naay computer, so musud lang na sila mu access sa computer then ipakita ang presentation, human na. Lecture na na, so kana amu teacher magda ra lagi na ug ballpen manud, so kada classroom naa gyud na sila di ta pareha ani nga magbitbit pa ta sa atong projector, mag set-up pa ta, ana so inig sud nila, mo-log-in sa computer, deretso na presentation, unya ang kanindot pud nila kay smart smart bitaw ang ilang ilang board, murag bag blackboard day nga while nakaproject dinha pwede ka diha magsuwat suwat... Oh, smart tawag ana smart, oh interactive mga ingana. Pwede ka magcompute unya makita ang imung kinomputan, oh ingana so ma-amaze ko. Unya muingun ko, How I wish.

-Teacher 11

(... in Europe because I was able to get a scholarship and study there for six months no, in Czech Republic, their classrooms are nice, the teachers when they come to class only bring ballpen and a small paper, why? Each classroom has a smart board wherein you will write...it is interactive, then, their projector is already embedded and has a computer. So, the teachers attend to class, access the computer, show the presentation, and the lecture is done. That's it. Our teacher only brings a ballpen when he comes to class, unlike here, we have to bring our projector to class and has to set up the equipment. There, when they come to class they log in the computer, and directly project their presentation. Another good thing there is the smart board, it is like a blackboard, however, while you're projecting your presentation you can write, you can compute and your solution can be shown, I am amazed. Then, I can only say, how I wish...)

Even though the interactive whiteboard is valuable as it aids in improving students' learning, promoting literacy, boosting attentiveness, and increasing comprehension of the learners (Clark, 2012; Cox, 2019), only a few universities in the Philippines use this tool (Bonifacio, 2013). As observed, the research locales could not provide this technological tool, much so install one in their classrooms. Figure 11 shows a typical classroom setup in the research locales. The setup was not surprising since there had been instances when the basic, four-walled room was not even possible, as seen in Figure 12, with a makeshift classroom in one of the research locales. The probable reasons could include: the interactive whiteboards and installation being expensive and the training for teachers on how to use this tool would require scarce resources (e.g., training funds and ample time for the training).

Figure 11

A Classroom in One of the Research Locales

Figure 12

A Makeshift Classroom in One of the Research Locales

Other Multimedia Materials Used by the Teacher Participants. Interestingly, the teacher participants responded that they utilized audio clips, sound excerpts, and public service announcements as technological tools, which are short informational clips meant to raise awareness about an important topic (PSU, 2017) in delivering their lessons. Public service announcements (either used or presented in audio-only or audio-visual form) enable students to apply discipline-specific knowledge, develop persuasion strategies, gain technical skills, think creatively, and develop a sense of teamwork (Abrams, 2012). Therefore, it was assumed that this multimedia material could be observed as the participants' statements suggested their recognition of how such materials can help deliver lessons on Purposive Communication. Unfortunately, there was no instance of using such materials during the observation sessions, so this study relied only on the teachers' interview responses:

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“Through videos, audios, hasta kanang sa kuan lagi ila book nga kanang mga video na assignment then ako pud gamitun I make use pud na or idownload nako ang uban para ipakita nila”

-Teacher 2

(Through videos, audios, even the videos in the books indicated as assignment, I used it or I download others to show to my students)

“...I did present one of my diagnostic tests kadtong ang audio nga it's I want them to get the, the message or mura siyag interview of some sort...”

-Teacher 6

(...I did present one of my diagnostic tests that audio it's I want them to get the message or it's like an interview of some sort...)

Generally, the multimedia materials used by the teacher participants fall under the standalone multimedia materials based on the category identified by Abdularahaman et al. (2020), as discussed in chapter 2. The multimedia materials used in the classes were all downloaded before the actual teaching sessions and did not rely on access to the internet during the sessions. For the examples, refer to Figures 4, 8 and 15. How the multimedia materials were prepared and provided to the students reflected teacher participants' limitations in exploring supposedly more advanced, web-based multimedia materials and tools. The teacher participants' use of multimedia materials and how they were used can be further analyzed based on Laurillard's (2002) media types in accordance with the learning experiences they support, as seen in Table 8.

Table 8

The Multimedia Materials used by the Teacher Participants, Its Media Types, Learning Types and the Learning Experiences it Support

Types of Learning	Learning experience	Multimedia resources utilized by the teacher participants	Media types
Acquisition	Attending, apprehending	PowerPoint presentations, television shows, digital flip charts and other infographics, excerpts or articles from e-magazines, music videos, movies, audio clips, video talks from lecture series or conferences	Narrative
Investigation	Investigating, exploring	Educational links or web pages	Interactive
Discussion	Discussing, debating	Blogs, vlogs or screencasts, FB group chats	Communicative
Practice	Experimenting, practicing	Mobile and/ computer games/apps	Adaptive
Production	Articulating, expressing	Public service announcements	Productive

It could be inferred from the data that most multimedia materials are narrative media types, meaning that the teacher participants used mostly linear presentational media. Being linear, the materials and the activities surrounding them were non-interactive (Laurillard, 2002). In other words, this media offers only descriptions of the topics, mainly from the teachers' point of view (Laurillard, 2002). However, Laurillard (2002) mentioned that despite the narrative media type only supporting the mere acquisition of information, teachers could structure the narrative to engage the learners in reflecting and articulating thoughts on the lessons. The learners may also be encouraged to assume roles in adapting and acting experiences. This means the teachers can still explore other strategies using these media types, thereby elevating

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the learning experience. Moreover, it is noticeable that the teacher participants employed methods or multimedia materials that are computer-based instead of the traditional technologies introduced originally by Laurillard (2002). These multimedia resources are classified into different media types. Some teacher participants also used educational links or webpages under the interactive media. As discussed in Chapter 2, this media form supports investigating and exploring learning experiences and is nonlinear in nature (Laurillard, 2002).

The classification of the multimedia materials utilized would not suffice our understanding of multimedia use; hence another sub-theme emerged from the data, and this sub-theme is concerned with how exactly the multimedia were integrated.

Parts of the Lesson the Multimedia Materials were Integrated. In addition to finding out what kind of multimedia materials was used and how often, the study also attempted to find out from the teacher participants which part of the lesson and how exactly the multimedia materials were integrated. Most teacher participants responded that multimedia materials were often integrated during discussion, and fewer employed multimedia materials to assess students' learning. Moreover, a teacher participant replied that multimedia materials were integrated to clarify a point (See Table 9).

Table 9

Parts of the Lesson the Multimedia Materials were Integrated

Parts of the Lesson	Number of Teacher Participants	Percentage
During discussion	16	94%
Introducing a topic	15	88%
Motivating the students	13	76%
Assessing the students' learning	9	53%
Others: To clarify my point	1	6%

From the observation, the integration of multimedia materials was noted in the different parts of the lesson: from introducing a topic and motivating students during the discussion to assessing the students' learning. These the teacher participants affirmed such observations in the interview.

Motivating the Students. One of the crucial parts of a lesson is the motivation component, where the teacher can get the learners' attention by activating their schema and preparing them for the lesson (Filgona et al., 2020; Golland, 1998; McQuown, 2011;). The use of efficient strategies can aid teachers in motivating students well. The data revealed that 76% of the teacher participants employed multimedia materials in this part of the lesson. Figure 13 shows teacher participants presenting a short video clip to activate the learners' schema about the topic. There were also teacher participants who mentioned that multimedia materials are suitable for rousing the interests of the students:

“sometimes I use it as a motivation part like when I, when the subject or the topic in purposive was a cultura--I differences. So I used a video showing how people differ in culture...”

-Teacher 9

Figure 13

A Teacher Participant Showing a Short Video Clip to Motivate the Students

Introducing a Topic. It was found that before any in-depth discussions and learning activities are conducted, the teachers would try to motivate the students and introduce the topic formally . This part of the lesson often includes a preliminary discussion that leads to the explanation or the main discussion (Cerbin & Kopp, 2006). Like in the motivation part of the lesson , using technological tools to present the introduction would seem efficient in preparing the students for the discussion (Pun, 2013). Figure 14 shows the use of a Powerpoint Presentation to introduce a topic. Based on the survey , eighty-eight percent (88%) of teacher participants used multimedia materials in this part of the lesson . The practice was also mentioned in the interviews:

“...Videos like before I start my discussion I would show them a three-minute video or if I cannot show that to them I will send them the link”
-Teacher 7

Figure 14

A Teacher Participant Integrating PowerPoint Presentation to Introduce a Topic

During Discussion. Most, if not all, of the teacher participants believed that the highlight of a lesson or class session was the actual discussion of the topic. Teachers may employ various teaching strategies and techniques that fit the topic and the students' needs (Abdulbaki et al., 2018). For this part, learners have an excellent opportunity to interact with the teachers and their peers by asking questions and sharing answers, supposedly deepening their understanding of a topic (Killen, 2007). Using multimedia materials in this part could also lead to increased learner motivation, enhanced communicative competence, and widened knowledge of both the topic and the target language (Good & Jarvenin, 2007; Ketsman, 2012; Pun, 2013; Susikaran, 2013). The multimedia materials also help create a more conducive learning and

teaching environment (Pun, 2013; Susikaran, 2013). In the context of the interview and observation sessions conducted, 94% of the teacher participants used multimedia materials in this manner. Figures 4 and 8 show some teacher participants using multimedia materials like videos, e-magazines, and PowerPoint Presentations as aids. During the interview, the teacher participants cited motivating the learners, getting their attention, and making the lessons more meaningful as the common reasons for using multimedia materials like so:

“I used multimedia for additional motivation...I used multimedia after the discussion if we will have an activity or during the discussion for example we discussed about the types of speeches and the modes of- modes of speeches, so we have we during uh the discussion there was uhm a speaker and the television for the different examples of the different types of speeches...”

-Teacher 13

“For me ma'am it's very important and it's very uh what do you call this uhm catching, if you would say if you would you would use technology because if you will just use the mouth or the discussion itself I would say that even me as a teacher or even me as a student uhm I would say that the lesson would be very boring if the teacher would just this and that and bla bla bla bla bla, so uh because for us in the Philippines we are visual learners so I would say or I would always use technology if there is technology or if I am allowed to use it so, I would really have more time in downloading or researching materials for my lessons”

-Teacher 15

Assessing the Students' Learning. Fifty-three percent (53%) of the teacher participants utilized multimedia materials to assess their students' learning. Figure 15 exhibits the use of multimedia materials in the assessment part of the lesson. There were also teacher participants who expressed in the interviews that multimedia materials were used during assessment:

“I also sometimes I use video or a powerpoint presentation in the discussion part... sometimes for the evaluation part as well....”

-Teacher 9

“...discussion gyud siya kay mao lagi to anindot man gud pud siya sa part nga evaluation...”

-Teacher 10

(...in the discussion, though it will also be okay in the evaluation part...)

Figure 15

A Teacher Participant Using Multimedia During Assessment

From the findings, it was noted that the learning assessment part is essential because it aids the teachers in evaluating the learning acquired by the learners, measuring the success of the strategy or tools used, and weighing the skill or topic that was less developed or understood (Umar, 2018). The multimedia materials can also be used to carry out this part of the lesson.

It was observed and noted that the teacher participants deliberately used multimedia resources to meet the needs of 21st century learners. The participants'

claims alluded to the recognition that technology is one of the best aids to enhance the lesson, entice students to pay attention, and improve students' language skills. This assertion is supported by numerous studies on technology integration, especially in language classrooms (Chinnery, 2006; Conroy, 2010; Good & Jarvenin, 2007; Ketsman, 2012; Levine et al., 2000; Ramchandran, 2004). These scholars and researchers proved that technology integration like multimedia materials provides many benefits in language teaching and learning.

To understand how the multimedia materials were integrated further, a third sub-theme emerged from the data, which relates to technology integration models.

Technology Integration Model. The data showed that the teacher participants must have knowledge of technology, pedagogy, and content to succeed in teaching Purposive Communication. Specifically, it would seem that TPK would be one aspect that the teachers need to hone continually. It is not enough for them to know what technologies to use; they should also know how to use these technologies, especially multimedia resources, to deliver the lessons more meaningfully. The RAT and TPACK models were used as frameworks to understand the teacher participants' actual practices better. The extent to which the teacher participants use multimedia materials was first identified based on the descriptors in the RAT model. However, only four out of the six dimensions of the RAT model were included as they directly relate to the teachers' practices of integrating multimedia materials. Table 10 on the next page summarizes how the teacher participants utilize multimedia materials based on the dimensions of instruction.

Table 10*The Extent of Multimedia Materials Integration of the Teacher Participants*

Dimensions of Instruction	Extent of Integration		
	Replacement	Amplification	Transformation
Teacher's Role in Instruction	The teacher participants assure the suitable use of multimedia materials in the classroom.	The teacher participants act as guide in the use of multimedia as these materials are integrated in the lessons.	Under the set objectives, the teacher participants facilitate the use of multimedia materials
Interaction with Students	The teacher participants employ multimedia materials in order to present lessons like the use of PowerPoint presentations	Teacher participants inspire the learners to employ multimedia materials like integrating activities through multimedia like blogs or vlogs	The teacher participants allow students to create something that is made possible through the use of multimedia materials. The creation of public service announcements could be an example of this category.
Assessment of students	Multimedia materials utilized to project assessment through PowerPoint Presentation, which is not a pure replacement to the traditional method of conducting assessments	Teacher participants may use various multimedia like infographics to conduct assessment.	Teacher participants may utilize multimedia materials in order to come up with diverse and meaningful outputs
Instructional Preparation	Teacher participants understand the salient features of the multimedia materials, however, there is still a lack of meaningful utilization in the classroom.	Teacher participants are already familiar and are fully exposed to various forms of multimedia, though enhancement in the integration is still essential.	Teacher participants gain proficiency in integrating multimedia materials, which were acquired through professional development like training.

Based on the descriptors, most of how the teachers integrated multimedia as the technology falls under *replacement*, though a few demonstrated *amplification*- and *transformation*-related activities. From the interviews, most of the teacher participants had difficulty amplifying and transforming their lessons using multimedia. This finding implies that the level of TK among teacher participants remains relatively low. Despite this, the solid attempts of the teacher participants were noted from the observation—Most tried to make use of the technological tools (i.e., available devices) and resources (e.g., various multimedia) as they delivered the lessons. There were learning activities facilitated with multimedia that tried to engage the students. This finding seems consistent with previous studies on technology integration (Ersanli, 2016; Kose, 2016; Mahdum, 2015; Tai, 2013). In any case, ensuring that teachers of a language and communication course such as Purposive Communication have sufficient knowledge of the essential content, technologies available, and how such technologies may be used more meaningfully in relation to the content remains a priority. With this scenario, it is natural to look at the typical challenges of the teacher participants and the mechanisms to address them.

Challenges Encountered in Using Multimedia Materials and Actions Taken to Address the Challenges

Challenges Experienced by the Teacher Participants in Using Multimedia Materials. Despite the teacher participants' interest in integrating multimedia materials into their lessons, some factors limited their practices. These factors were summarized as the third theme from the data, the challenges encountered by the teachers in integrating multimedia materials and the relevant solutions sought.

The data from the survey showed that troubleshooting with the devices is the commonly experienced barrier by the participants. However, fewer teacher participants experienced challenges in navigating apps and software. Some participants cited concerns not pre-listed in the survey, such as lack of equipment to deliver content (e.g., laptops, projectors, and the like), the durability of the available equipment, power outages, and slow internet connection. Figure 16 summarizes the challenges and concerns of the teacher participants related to multimedia integration.

Figure 16

Challenges Encountered by The Teacher Participants in Using Multimedia

Materials

A few excerpts from the interviews are also cited to elaborate on these challenges mentioned:

“Ahh, my very first is that syempre hinay atong internet dinhi whenever you research something with a specific topic usahay kamang pa sa turtle, so kana one issue”

–Teacher 3

(Ahh, my very first is we have a slow internet here, whenever you research something with a specific topic sometimes slower than a turtle, so that is one issue)

“we don't have the- how do you call this, a hundred percent access of wi-fi, that really hinders us to bring out the best in us.... I could hardly connect to the wi-fi connections from this university”

–Teacher 8

“...loading ang internet, yeah, and of course we don't have a you cannot, you cannot deny that fact that sometimes our laptop would be mag-hang siya...”

—Teacher 2

“so kadtong the u- diba we use of multimedia or the use of technology diba it needs electricity, so kanang it's very difficult here kanang if there will be no electricity or there will be some technical problems...”

—Teacher 4

(so, we use multimedia or use technology right? it needs electricity, so it is very difficult here if there will be no electricity or there will be some technical problems...)

“...uhm power outage, so there is no electricity and I cannot use the projector for example to present my video and sometimes if there's no internet connection, so I cannot download the materials that I- I need to use.”

-Teacher 9

“we lack technology and kung buot huna hunaun gyud kay di gyud nato ma-acheive gyud unta ang when it comes to technology maam”

-Teacher 7

(we lack technology and we could not achieve the objectives of the course when it comes to technology ma'am)

“aw no the projectors but then the projectors are used by other instructors and then you cannot borrow it.”

—Teacher 15

“easy access sa internet just like sa office timing usa na kami ka semanang walay internet, diba and you need to download, you need to ano i- if my internet na ang campus you do not need to download anymore to the internet kay automatic nana, straight from the ano... What else, uh campus equipment pa, not all classrooms would provide our own techno, would provide our own uh laptops, our own- kanang equipment, I- I wish na nay mga television sets, screen ba para namo, because we won't need our projector so mao na...”

-Teacher 17

(easy internet access just like in the office, it is already one week that we do not have internet. Then, you need to download. If there is internet in the campus, you do not need to download anymore, you can present directly straight from the source. What else, campus equipment also, not all classrooms have techno, we would provide our own laptops, our own equipment, I wish we have television sets, screen, so we won't need our projector, that's it...)

Some researchers proved that these challenges are also experienced by other teachers who employed technology in their classroom across the globe (Albirini, 2006; Empirica, 2006; Pelgrum, 2001; Silicia, 2005).

The Most Common Challenge Experienced by the Teacher Participants.

Seventy-two-point twenty-two percent (72.22%) indicated that they experienced troubleshooting their devices. This finding was also noted during class observations (See Figures 17 and 18) and interviews, as shown in the excerpts below:

“nay corrupted unsahay ang file ana ba unya Unsahay di mo-play or kanang mga wiring...”

—Teacher 12

(there are corrupted files, sometimes it would not play or probably have problems with the wiring...)

“But then, I experienced that my laptop di siya mu connect so I, I tried using VGA and then HDMI, VGA nga naay adaptor nga HDMI di jud siya muconnect...”

—Teacher 6

(But then, I experienced that my laptop could not connect to the projector, I tried using VGA and then HDMI, VGA with an adaptor but it would not connect...)

Troubleshooting problems are often associated with the inability of the teachers to address issues in using devices, such as how to adjust the light of the DLP projector, how to deal with the laptop computers when a video would not play/ project on the screen, and some other concerns (Johnson et al., 2016; Ramorola, 2013). Some researchers and scholars indicated that there are weighty reasons behind troubleshooting problems with devices in the language classroom, including, but not limited to, the unavailability of policy on technology use, technophobia among teachers, gap in digital knowledge, and lack of training (Gupta, 2017; Hyndman, 2018; Ramorola, 2013). In the case of the teacher participants, the reasons for troubleshooting problems cited are the gap in digital knowledge and lack of training on how to use the technological devices.

“...their instinct as 21st century communicators, especially nowadays they are very receptive when in terms to technology and how they use gadgets daily, it's very overwhelming.”

-Teacher 5

“Technology illiterate man ko ui.”

-Teacher 10

(I am technology illiterate.)

“And then, sometime pud maam, naa puy sometimes na I don't have knowledge maam how to... how to do ana...(set up)”

-Teacher 4

(And then, sometimes also ma'am, there are some times that I don't have the knowledge ma'am how to... how to set up)

“...di gyud na nato ma achieve ma'am kay even ako as, as an instructor I don't have much knowledge about mga how to use this ano, ana...”

-Teacher 7

(... we can't achieve it ma'am, even I as an instructor I don't have much knowledge about how to use this what, like that...)

Figure 17

A Teacher Participant Encountering a Problem with the Display while Doing a Lecture

Figure 18

A teacher participant having trouble with the screen projection

The Challenge Least Experienced by the Teacher Participants. Twenty-seven point seventy-eight percent (27.78%) of the participants specified that they experienced difficulty navigating apps or software. Navigating apps or any available software is essential in integrating technology in the language classroom since an increasing number of apps, software, and programs can aid the teachers in guiding the students well during discussion (Edutopia, 2007). The researcher did not observe the teacher participants experiencing this problem during the class observation, perhaps because they were not provided with such resources in the first place, as tabulated in Table 3. The teacher participants could not use web-based multimedia materials during the class and mostly used standalone multimedia materials. From the interviews, the teacher participants favored standalone tools and materials over web-based ones because there is limited access to the internet, which is a requirement for successful use (Abdulrahman et al., 2020). Despite their desire to incorporate some

web-based materials, they could only explore those with offline versions and incorporate them into the resources they themselves prepared.

Classification of Challenges Experienced by the Teacher Participants in Using Multimedia Materials. Classifying the identified challenges may help understand the common challenges better, so a classification guide from a study by van Braak (2001) was used in the analysis. The challenges encountered by the teacher participants based on the data can be classified into material and finance, school-specific, and support categories. The lack of available equipment like Interactive whiteboards, DLP projectors, laptop, and TV screen fall under material and finance. This challenge alluded to insufficient funding to provide practical and effective technological tools. The challenge on the class schedule, on the other hand, is classified as school-specific. The school-specific category is defined as a challenge related to the curriculum or program specific to the institution. Thus, the number of hours assigned for each subject and the hours the instructors are required to report in the office are concrete examples of this challenge. The problems with troubleshooting, downloading, and installing devices and equipment are under the support type. One of the possible reasons teachers encounter these challenges is the lack of external support. Without assistance in the form of training and technical aid, there were teacher participants who could not deliver their lessons successfully using technology; In fact, there were few who admitted in the interview that they lacked the knowledge on how to operate and navigate technological devices.

Additionally, contrary to a common belief that the government provides state universities with advanced technological tools to deliver the lessons well, especially with the offering of core GE courses, the research locales have fewer available

resources to utilize. As identified in the data, one of the challenges experienced by the teacher participants in delivering their lessons was the lack of available equipment like Interactive whiteboards, DLP or LCD projectors, laptops, or TV screens. This situation is also true for other government-run schools in other countries (Silicia, 2005; Toprakci, 2006).

Actions Taken by the Teacher Participants to Address the Challenges Encountered. To counter the obstacles, the teacher participants had also taken actions to address these. The solutions taken by the teacher participants were almost the same as the suggestions provided by the previous researchers (Bingimlas, 2009; Fajardo, 2014; Gilakjani, 2012; Johnson et al., 2016; ZHANG, 2016).

From the survey data, most teacher participants sought help and considered their previous experiences to address the obstacles in using multimedia materials. Others used the internet to search for solutions; some relied on their knowledge from training. In addition, some teacher participants also indicated other alternative solutions not included in the survey options which include: look for an alternative (plan B) or use other strategies; print the instructional materials (IMs) needed for the lesson; prepare materials in advance; come to class 5-10 minutes in advance to have enough time to set up the DLP projector; ask a student to create group chat on messenger, where the teacher participant shares the multimedia materials to be used for the class (See Figure 19 for details).

Figure 19

Solutions Employed by the Teacher Participants to Address the Challenges Experienced in Using Multimedia Materials

Commonly Used Solutions in Dealing with the Challenges of Using Multimedia Materials. The survey data revealed that 61.11% of the teacher participants opted to seek help from others and consider their previous experiences in addressing the challenges they experienced in using multimedia materials. Seeking help from others and considering previous experiences are practical solutions to deal with the teachers' challenges in integrating technology in the language classroom (Johnson et al., 2016). The classroom observation notes complemented the results of the survey. As observed, there were teacher participants who sought the help of their students to resolve technical issues. Also, teacher participants resolved the challenge encountered using their previous experiences (See Figures 17 & 18). Based on previous research, these solutions are applicable to address the challenges encountered by the respondents as these are time-saving, efficient, and practical

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(Bingimlas,2009; Fajardo, 2014; Gilakjani, 2012). Also, the teacher participants' responses during the interview supported these survey responses:

“...so manawag na ko ug students assist maam kanang inig set-up sa projector, or sa kuan di ko kahibawo, so mao gyud na ang kuan, challenge gyud na nahu maam.”

-Teacher 4

(...so I call students who can assist me, ma'am, to set up the projector or when I don't know, so that is really a challenge for me, ma'am)

Figure 20

An Instance When One Teacher Participants Sought the Help of One of the Students to Troubleshoot Technical Issues

Least Used Solutions in Dealing with the Challenges in Using Multimedia Materials. Thirty-three point thirty-three percent (33.33%) of the teacher participants relied on the knowledge acquired from training to address their challenges. Acquisition of knowledge through training is necessary for the technology integration in the language classroom to be well delivered (Torsani, 2016). Through meaningful training,

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teachers can further their understanding and skills, which they can utilize in the actual situation (Marek,2014). Fewer teacher participants used this type of solution since there were teacher participants who were fresh graduates during the conduct of the study. Thus, it is expected that they could not attend training related to technology integration yet. Possibly, the lack of proper training on technology integration could be why few teacher participants used this solution.

Other Solutions Sought. As cited earlier, the teacher participants indicated that they employed other solutions to address their challenges aside from the solutions pre-listed in the survey. These solutions included exploring a plan B or other strategies, preparing the materials in advance, coming to class to set up the equipment, using other platforms like group chat, and using printed materials, as reflected in the following interview excerpts:

“Akong strategy maam is sometimes there is no available na DLP, uhm I will tell them to download a copy of this, so while since I will not be having a DLP, so while I'm discussing this one you can open your cellphones and then, open the downloaded file that I sent you so we can be at the same ano ba,ingana. So murag use that nalang maam especially that here in our department we lack resources.”

-Teacher 7

(My strategy ma'am when there is no available DLP, I will tell my students to download a copy of this, so while I'm discussing it they can open their cellphones and open the downloaded file I sent. So, we can be at the same phase. So, I use it ma'am, especially that here in our department we lack resources.)

“So, come to class on time para you have enough time to set up para di makuhaan ang imung one hour nga kuwang ra for purposive actually, hmn maputol gyud siya, maputol.”

-Teacher 11

(So, come to class on time so that I have enough time to set up. So, my one hour for Purposive Communication will not be deducted, or else the lesson will be cut.)

The actions taken by the teacher participants to address the challenges are short-term solutions. Since the challenges related to material and finance and school-specific concerns require amendments to the institutions' budget, guidelines, and other programs which require approval from authorities, the teacher participants, with their initiative, adopted schemes that helped them resolve the issues (Abdulrahaman et al., 2020). Requiring students to download the multimedia materials in advance using their mobile phones, coming to class ahead of the class schedule to set up the equipment, and making use of a plan B or other teaching strategies are some of the valuable solutions adopted by the teacher participants in their classrooms. For the support-related challenges, the teacher participants sought help from their students and colleagues who may be more technologically proficient. Relying on prior knowledge and current skills acquired from previous training is considered a quick but also a short-term response to technical challenges. In this regard, institutions still need to initiate training and other professional development programs that can help the teachers with technology integration and troubleshooting any technical issues (Gilakjani, 2012).

One promising finding is that despite the challenges faced by the teacher participants, they exerted effort to address those challenges in an attempt to meet the goal of the course, which is to prepare the learners for the challenging demands of the contemporary world by developing their skills through technology like multimedia materials (Mayer & Moreno, 2003). Against this backdrop, an updated policy or simply a professional development program for higher education teachers, especially

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designed for the language and communication teachers of Purposive Communication, may be a worthwhile solution. The last chapter elaborates on this.

Chapter V

Summary, Conclusions, and Recommendations

This chapter presents the summary of the study, the conclusion formulated from the study's findings, and the recommendations identified to enrich the study on technology integration in the language classroom. This chapter provides a detailed overview of the study, including conclusions made based on the analysis of the data. This chapter also presents recommendations that future researchers, teachers, or experts could consider in exploring further technology integration in the language classroom at the tertiary level.

Summary

As there is a growing demand for globally competitive graduates, the Commission on Higher Education (CHED) developed more condensed GE courses for the revised curriculum. One of these courses is Purposive Communication, the only language course offered as part of the revised GE curriculum. This course aimed to holistically develop the learners' five macro-skills using multimedia materials within the implementation of the lessons.

Since technology in the language classroom remains uncommon in some areas of the country, a gap in knowledge and literature on using multimedia materials in teaching Purposive Communication was observed. Thus, looking into the practices and perceptions of college English teachers on using multimedia materials in the language classroom is timely and relevant. In addition, this study identified and categorized the teaching strategies of the language teachers in teaching Purposive Communication, classified the multimedia materials they used, and provided an integration model which may be used as a guide by the language teachers. The study

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also identified the challenges encountered by language teachers in integrating multimedia materials and the approaches adopted to address the challenges.

This study could aid in understanding the practices of using multimedia materials in delivering lessons by assessing how the teachers incorporate multimedia. The study could act as an operational manual for teachers to identify teaching strategies, type of multimedia materials, level of integration, and even the challenges in using multimedia materials so they could weigh better on how they may incorporate multimedia materials in their lessons.

With the recent changes in the academe brought about by the pandemic, the shift to the blended type of teaching may also be challenging to some teachers. Hence, this study may be used to identify teaching strategies and apt approaches in integrating multimedia materials within face-to-face or blended classrooms. Moreover, taking into account the assessment of how multimedia materials were utilized, this study may contribute to the growing literature on the use of multimedia materials in the language classroom.

There were three state universities considered as research locales of the study, located in the Western and Southern parts of Leyte (Visayas Region of the Philippines). The researcher employed purposive sampling in selecting the participants of the study. Seventeen (17) teacher participants agreed to participate fully in the study.

The study adopted hermeneutical phenomenology to capture the real-life experiences and perceptions of the English teacher on the use of multimedia materials in the classroom. Three research instruments were used: a preliminary survey, in-

depth one-on-one interviews, and class observations. For the researcher to extract answers from the data, thematic analysis was utilized. Through the aid of Atlas.ti software, the coding process was done smoothly. The researcher still identified significant phrases and statements, assigned codes to specific themes, and integrated the overall themes.

The findings of the study are summarized based on the statement of the problems mentioned in Chapter 1.

1. What strategies are used by selected language teachers in teaching Purposive Communication?

The first theme from the thematic analysis was the strategies used by language teachers in teaching Purposive Communication. The preliminary survey, classroom observation, and interview results are the same. Most teacher participants employed lectures as a strategy. Fewer teacher participants used the seminar as a strategy for teaching Purposive Communication. In addition, they resorted to other teaching strategies, which they believed fit the students' needs and assisted them in attaining both the course and lesson objectives. The other strategies they used were individual or group reporting, oral recitation, and multimedia materials like videos and audio. Their strategies in teaching Purposive Communication fall under the teacher-centered type based on the category identified by Makokha and Ongwae (2001). Though the teacher participants attempted to make the lessons participative by incorporating multimedia and interactive activities to attain the course's objectives.

2. How do the teachers use or integrate multimedia materials in teaching Purposive Communication?

The second theme which came up during the thematic analysis was the integration of multimedia materials in teaching Purposive Communication. It was then subdivided into three sub-themes: the multimedia materials used, the integration of the multimedia, and the technology integration model adopted.

The data showed that most of the teacher participants typically utilized PowerPoint Presentations in teaching the course; incorporated in their presentation were downloaded videos, e-magazine clips, links, and animations. Most teacher participants used standalone multimedia materials based on the category identified by Abdulrahman et al. (2020) since they downloaded multimedia materials instead of using web-based materials directly during class. At the same time, teacher participants had never used interactive whiteboards because this technological tool was unavailable in their institutions. In addition, most of the multimedia utilized fall under the narrative media form based on Laurillard's (2002) classification. Since most of the multimedia materials used are linear, this supports the acquisition type of learning.

Though it was noted and observed that multimedia materials were integrated into the different parts of the lesson, most teacher participants indicated in the survey that they mainly used it for introducing a topic and during discussions with the students. A limited number of teacher participants employed multimedia materials to assess their students' learning.

The teacher participants were motivated to use multimedia materials in teaching the course to improve the learners' language skills; to entice the learners to

pay attention during discussions; to avoid boredom among students, and to expose the learners to the different ways of the world.

Regarding the technology integration model, the data revealed that the relationship between knowledge of technology, pedagogy, and content is significant in using multimedia materials in the language classroom successfully. The RAT model was used to assess the teacher participants' TK. Data revealed that most teacher participants were only at the replacement stage of using multimedia materials. However, a few teacher participants amplified and attempted to transform their lessons through multimedia materials. In summary, a balanced knowledge of appropriate technological tools, teaching strategies, and content is vital to deliver the lessons effectively. As observed and noted from the data, the teacher participants aimed to improve their TPACK by actively exploring the possibilities of multimedia integration beyond replacement to attain the course outcomes and enrich the learners' skills.

3. How do the teachers address the challenges they face in integrating multimedia materials in teaching Purposive Communication?

The third theme from the analysis was subdivided into two: the challenges faced and actions taken by the teacher participants in using multimedia materials.

Most teacher participants experienced troubleshooting problems with devices or equipment. The least experienced issue in using multimedia materials in teaching Purposive Communication was navigating apps or software. The possible reason behind this could be that the multimedia materials used are stand-alone tools. Thus, the challenges experienced are based on these tools.

These challenges are categorized into *material and finance*, *school-specific*, and *support*, as van Braak (2001) identified. The lack of available equipment, slow

internet connection, and power supply issues fall under *material and finance*. While the issue of the use of multimedia materials consuming too much time during the class period is under the *school-specific* category. The challenges of troubleshooting devices, looking for suitable materials, installing equipment, and downloading relevant materials are under the *support* category.

The majority of teacher participants resorted to short-term solutions/ approaches to deliver the lessons using multimedia materials since most of the challenges under *material and finance* and *school-specific* need established resolutions from corresponding authorities. Specifically, the teacher participants actively resolved their obstacles, albeit provisionally. Some of these solutions or coping strategies included adjusting to the class schedule and resorting to other strategies and available resources that are immediately available, like mobile phones. In the case of *support-related* challenges, the teacher participants sought help from their students and colleagues and relied on the knowledge acquired from prior experiences.

Considering the study's findings, a program for enhancing the learning materials and the TK and skills of the teachers was proposed. "TEACHnology 2.0," as a midyear break camp, is recommended to develop teachers' knowledge of different multimedia materials and the more appropriate way of integrating them.

Conclusions

Based on the indicated findings, the following conclusions were drawn:

1. The teacher participants mainly used lectures, specifically multimedia and interactive, to teach Purposive Communication.

2. The teaching strategies employed by the teacher participants can be categorized under the *teacher-centered* category though they attempted to make their lessons more interactive or participative.
3. The teacher participants have a positive perception of the use of multimedia materials in the classroom; they regularly used PowerPoint Presentations (with video clips, clips from e-magazines, photos and audios incorporated) in delivering their lessons in Purposive Communication.
4. Most of the multimedia materials used by the teacher participants fall under the *narrative* type of media form, which supports the acquisition type of learning.
5. Lack of resources often hindered participants from exploring web-based multimedia materials.
6. Based on instructional descriptors, most teacher participants used multimedia under the *replacement* stage, though a few used multimedia to amplify and transform the lessons. Additionally, the findings revealed that most teacher participants have low TK, but their CK and PK did not come up as an issue. Nevertheless, they would need assistance to improve their TK and TPK.
7. The teacher participants resorted to alternative solutions or short-term and trial-and-error strategies to address the challenges.
8. The results of the study could serve as a springboard for a program focused on multimedia materials enhancement and on a faculty

development program called “TEACHnology” to develop the teachers' TK and TPK.

Recommendations

This study unveiled the practices and perceptions of selected College language teachers on using multimedia materials in teaching the core GE course for language, Purposive Communication. Based on the analysis of the findings, the following recommendations are presented:

For the Teachers of Purposive Communication

- The teachers should seek opportunities to reflect critically to see the potential of using multimedia materials, and other technologies, which may help enhance the delivery of lessons in Purposive Communication.
- The teachers need to engage actively with the current trends in teaching strategies and technology use through participation in seminars and training and involvement in research to keep abreast with the changes in the 21st century classroom.

For the Curriculum Developers and Instructional Material Designers

- Due to disruptions like the COVID-19 pandemic, significant shifts and adjustments in the higher education curriculum in the Philippines and abroad have emphasized the relevance of exploring affordances that can be provided with the help of ICTs (Bouilheres et al., 2020; Joaquin et al., 2020; Lapitan et al., 2021). One significant change is the emphasis on blended learning and teaching, which relies heavily on various ICTs to enrich the class within the traditional, physical classrooms and beyond (Alvarez, 2020; Bhowmik et al., 2019; Bond et al., 2018; Ahmed et al.,

2019; Willis et al., 2019). Specifically for teaching Purposive Communication, multimedia materials, tools, and apps are deemed essential to enhance the lessons. Noting this, curriculum developers and instructional material designers may need to reevaluate suggestions for multimedia materials and ways to use them, considering the available resources in higher education institutions in the Philippines, especially those state colleges and universities in rural areas.

- Also, they may need to engage with the College teachers from the ground more actively to help them be more knowledgeable in using ICTs, particularly multimedia materials.

University Administrators

- The state universities should provide opportunities for teachers to upgrade their knowledge of innovative teaching strategies and other advanced multimedia materials available and effective and more suitable approaches to technology integration.
- The administrators of state universities should support the teachers handling the core GE course, Purposive Communication, by prioritizing the enhancement and provision of the resources needed, like projectors, laptops, strong internet connection, and the like.

For the Commission on Higher Education

- The study's findings showed a gap in the TK and TPK of the teacher participants in relation to integrating multimedia materials more meaningfully. One reason could be the lack of training and seminars on ICT integration, specifically within the context of teaching the Purposive

Communication course. Considering the findings and the potential move towards blended learning and teaching, an enhanced and more comprehensive national policy must be developed so that the teachers would more actively improve their TPACK.

- In relation to an updated national policy, the Commission on Higher Education (CHED) should continually provide higher education institutions opportunities and funding to acquire the necessary resources needed for more successful technology integration in a language and communication course such as Purposive Communication.

For the Future Educational Researchers

- Comprehensive research should be considered in each research locale to guarantee the progress on the use of instructional innovations in Purposive Communication.
- Future educational researchers should explore further the use of multimedia materials in teaching Purposive Communication during this time when almost all Philippine Higher Education institutions are transitioning to technology-enhanced teaching.
- Future researchers should also consider the use of multimedia materials in other content areas, which are offered in the revised GE curriculum.

Recommended Professional Development Program

As observed and proven, technology has played a significant role in contemporary college classrooms. A number of policies on technology-enhanced teaching had been put in place even prior to the COVID-19 pandemic (Medina, 2018;

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Alvarez, 2020). Considering this, a program called "TEACHnology" may be explored. The term has been used as a website that provides free teaching sources for over a decade (Lynch, 2022). However, this term could be adopted to refer to a potential faculty development program to enhance the learning materials for Purposive Communication and improve the teachers' TPACK and practices of integrating various technologies. The idea is not new and has worked in other institutions. The term was used at the University of Massachusetts in early 2000 to link teaching and technology through a faculty development program (Shih & Sorcinelli, 2000). The "TEACHnology Fellowship Program" of the University of Massachusetts could be a promising framework for a training program either within the institutions used as the locale of this study or across Philippine Higher Education institutions.

Key features of the "TEACHnology" program that can serve as a guide for a localized and contextualized faculty development program for teachers of Purposive Communication include:

- the provision of incentives (recognition and rewards) for the development of relevant multimedia materials or technology-enhanced materials,
- strong emphasis on pedagogy (in the case of Purposive Communication, English language teaching and learning principles and strategies) and on acquiring new skills related to TPK instead of focusing on chasing after the latest technologies per se
- a range of individual support services,
- the creation of a collegial structure that facilitates dialogue,
- a clear guide on assessing technologies

With a version of the features cited above, the version for the Philippines can be a "TEACHnology 2.0," intended to be offered every midyear break for the teachers to have ample time to prepare for and focus on the actual program. Other features of the recommended program could include clearer, more relevant program goals, outcomes, and structures.

Program Goals and Expected Outcomes

To effectively integrate technology in the classroom, the following objectives of the program may be explored:

- to help teachers in higher education, especially those who are handling Purposive Communication, use suitable technological resources;
- to cultivate inclusivity and accessibility by prioritizing the needs of the faculty and students in order to innovate teaching through technology; and
- to provide an opportunity for professional development among faculty members.

In addition, the expected program outcomes may ask for the participants to:

1. acquire knowledge of different technological resources
2. recognize the various ways that ICTs can be integrated within lessons
3. deal with typical technical difficulties
4. form a network among participants with whom assistance can be sought
5. design course plans and lessons that make meaningful use of ICTs

Program Fellows and Features

The target participants of this midyear camp may be the university teachers or faculty members handling or will handle Purposive Communication. Depending on the institution's resources, other university teachers interested in and enthusiastic about

technology-enhanced teaching and learning may also be included as participants; however, it would be preferable to prepare a program specifically for language teachers since they are expected to understand signature pedagogies related to language teaching. Hence, the program's focus can be on improving their TK, and TCK, although CK, PK, and PCK may also be covered.

The structure of the program implemented in the University in Massachusetts was straightforward, and this version may adopt a simple approach. Potential participants will be provided with laptops pre-installed with relevant software, apps, and tools. All exercises may feature a refresher on essential language and communication principles and the pedagogical strategies that may seem suitable to adopt before relating them to the technology options available.

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APPENDICES

Appendix A1. Letter of Request

30 September 2019

Dr. Jett Quebec
Section Head, Languages Section
Department of Liberal Arts and Behavioral Sciences
Visayas State University
Visca, Bgy, Pangasugan, Baybay City, Leyte

Dear Dr. Quebec,

Greetings!

I am a graduate student of the University of the Philippines Open University (UPOU). I am currently in the process of writing my thesis entitled "**Practices and Perceptions of English Language Teachers on the Use of Multimedia Materials in a Communication Course in the Higher Education**", as one of the requirements for the degree Master of Arts in Language and Literacy Education (MALLE).

The purpose of this research is to explore how college English teachers utilize multimedia materials in teaching Purposive Communication by considering their practices and perceptions. The results of this study will potentially identify teaching strategies, various multimedia materials used, and challenges faced by the teachers in delivering the lessons of the new GE core course for language.

With this regard, I would like to ask permission from your good office to allow me to conduct my study in your department.

I am hoping for a positive response for this request.

Thank you for finding the time to read my letter.

Respectfully yours,

PAULA NADREA F. MORALES

Noted:

ANNA KATRINA MARCIAL
Thesis Adviser

Appendix A2. Consent Letter for the Participants

24 June 2019

Dear Participant,

Greetings!

I am a graduate student of the University of the Philippines Open University (UPOU). I am currently in the process of writing my thesis entitled “**Practices and Perceptions of English Language Teachers on the Use of Multimedia Materials in a Communication Course in the Higher Education**”, as one of the requirements for the degree Master of Arts in Language and Literacy Education (MALLE).

The purpose of this research is to explore how college English teachers utilize multimedia materials in teaching Purposive Communication by considering their practices and perceptions. The results of this study will potentially identify teaching strategies, various multimedia materials used, and challenges faced by the teachers in delivering the lessons of the new GE core course for language. With this regard, I am asking you to be a part of my study as a research participant.

If you choose to be a participant, I will ask about 60 minutes of personal time from you. You will complete fifteen questions from an initial questionnaire and will participate in a 30 to 45 minute interview. You will also be observed in the classroom by the researcher as you deliver your lesson in Purposive Communication.

Your participation in this research is completely voluntary and will not affect your employment. The researcher will not provide any monetary compensation. You may decline altogether, or leave if you don't wish to continue. There are no known risks to participation beyond those encountered in everyday life. Your responses will remain confidential and anonymous. No one, other than the researcher, will know your individual answers to the questionnaire, interview, and the results of the class observation.

I hope you will consider being a participant in this study. The researcher will provide a consent form, to know your response for this request.

If you have any questions about this study, feel free to contact the researcher.

Thank you for your assistance in this important endeavor.

Sincerely yours,

PAULA NADREA F. MORALES
09368687855
pnfm88@gmail.com

CONSENT FORM

Title of the study: Practices and Perceptions of English Language Teachers on the Use of Multimedia Materials for a Communication Course in Higher Education

Participant's pseudonym: _____

Date returned: _____

Please check the yes or no box for your reply. Please return as soon as possible.

Yes, I am participating in the study.

No, I am not participating in the study.

SIGNATURE: _____

Appendix B. Research Instruments
B1. *Preliminary Survey*

I. Demographic Profile

1. Name (Optional):

2. Age:

3. Highest Educational Attainment:

Bachelor's degree Master's degree Doctoral degree Postdoctoral degree

4. Designation:

Instructor Professor Assistant Professor Associate Professor

5. Employment Status:

Part-time Permanent Contractual Casual Regular Temporary Regular

6. Years of Experience as College English Teacher: _____

7. Field of Specialization: _____

8. Courses Previously Taught: _____

9. Have you ever received a training from CHED to teach Purposive Communication?

Yes

No

10. Have you received training/s or seminar/s other than offered by CHED, which you think help you in teaching Purposive Communication?

Yes

No

If yes, please indicate the title and organizer of the training/seminar.

Title of the Seminar/Training	Organizer

11. Please check (/) the teaching strategy/ies that you use in teaching Purposive Communication.

_____ Lecture _____ Discussion _____ Programmed
 instruction
 _____ Tutorial _____ Seminar _____ Demonstration
 _____ Buzz group _____ Brain storming _____ Role play
 _____ Study assignment (provide reading assignment)
 _____ Others, Please specify: _____

12. Do you use multimedia materials in teaching Purposive Communication?

Yes

No

If yes, please check (/) the multimedia material you use and how often you use the material in your teaching.

Multimedia Materials	Regularly (Daily)	Frequently (Weekly)	Occasionally (Monthly)	Seldom (Once every 2-3 Months)	Rarely (Once a Semester)	Never
1. Interactive Whiteboard						
1. Movies (either short clips or full)						
2. PowerPoint presentations						
3. Educational links/webpages						
4. Video talks from lecture series and /or conferences						
5. Mobile and /or computer games and/or app						

6. digital flipcharts						
7. television shows and/or advertisements						
8. e-newspapers/ e-magazines						
9. Music video						
10. blogs/vlogs						

Others, Please specify:

13. How do you integrate the multimedia materials in teaching Purposive Communication?

- _____ introducing a topic
- _____ motivating the students
- _____ during discussion
- _____ assessing the students' learning

_____ Others, please specify:

14. Have you ever experienced challenges in using multimedia materials in teaching Purposive Communication?

Yes No

If yes, what are the challenges you encountered?

- _____ installing the equipment like the overhead projector
- _____ downloading videos
- _____ time consuming

_____ looking for relevant multimedia materials for the topic/s
 _____ troubleshooting gadgets app
 _____ Others, please specify: _____

15. How do you address the challenges you encountered in using multimedia materials in teaching Purposive Communication?

_____ by seeking help from others (colleague or students)
 _____ by searching the internet
 _____ by considering previous experiences with the same technical issue
 _____ by relying on knowledge acquired from trainings
 _____ Others, please specify _____

B2. Class Observation Guide

Classroom Observation Notes

Teacher (Optional):

Time:

Date:

Degree Program of the Students:

Teaching Strategies	Ye s	N o	Observatio ns
1. The teacher understands how students learn and develop, and applies this knowledge in the teacher's practice. 2. The teacher employs multimedia to teach the lessons. 3. What are the teaching strategy/ies used by the teacher? a. Lecture b. Discussion c. Programmed instruction d. Tutorial e. Seminar f. Demonstration g. Buzz group h. Brain storming i. Role play j. Study assignment (provide reading assignment)			
Instructional Materials			Observatio ns

Practices and perceptions of English language teachers on the use of multimedia materials for a communication course in higher education

<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. The teacher knows efficient resources like multimedia materials to teach the lessons. 2. The teacher uses effectively the instructional materials in delivering the lessons. 3. The teacher uses multimedia materials in teaching Purposive Communication 4. What are the multimedia materials used by the teachers? <ol style="list-style-type: none"> a. Interactive Whiteboard b. Movies (either short clips or full) c. PowerPoint presentations d. Educational links/webpages e. Video talks from lecture series and /or conferences f. Mobile and /or computer games and/or app g. digital flipcharts h. television shows and/or advertisements i. e-newspapers/ e-magazines j. Music video k. blogs/vlogs 5. Did the teacher encountered problems in using multimedia materials? <ol style="list-style-type: none"> a. installing the equipment like the overhead projector b. downloading videos c. time consuming d. looking for relevant multimedia materials for the topic/s e. troubleshooting gadgets app 6. How did the teacher address the problem? <ol style="list-style-type: none"> a. by seeking help from others (colleague or students) b. by searching the internet c. by considering previous experiences with the same technical issue d. by relying on knowledge acquired from trainings 			
Assessment Methods			Observations
<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. The teacher facilitates, monitors, and assesses students' learning. 2. The teacher utilizes multimedia to assess the language improvements of the students. 			

B3. *Possible Interview Questions*

1. Did you participate in a training, seminar, or any other activity before you begin to teach Purposive Communication?
2. What are the specific teaching strategy/ies you used in teaching Purposive Communication?
3. Why do you employ such strategy/ies?
4. Have you employed technology in teaching Purposive Communication?
5. Can you describe the use of technology in teaching Purposive Communication?
6. Have you used multimedia materials in teaching Purposive Communication?
7. Which multimedia materials do you use?
8. In what part of your lesson do you integrate multimedia materials?
9. Were there any obstacles which hinder the use of multimedia materials in your class? If there are, can you describe/ enumerate.
10. What are your suggestions to solve the problems you faced?
11. Kindly share your thoughts about the multimodality nature of Purposive Communication.